

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Deliverable 10.1 – Founding principles of the Cloud Governance

HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01

Horizon Innovation action

Responsible authors :

Philippe Vendrix, Léna Czech (CNRS), Ad Pollé (EF), Charlotte Gallini, Rémi Petitcol (FSP), Elisabeth Stadlinger, Christoph Steindl, Anna Pühr (ONB), Elis Marçal (E.C.C.O.), Zoltan Szatucsek (NAH), Sam H. Minelli (META), Aleksandra Nowak (PSNC).

Project start	1 June 2024
Project duration	60 months
Document Identifier	10.5281/zenodo.17599162

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

ECHOES is a project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement n.101157364, with the support of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee n.10110142 & n.10110466.

Deliverable Information

Project Number	101157364	Acronym	ECHOES
Full title	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science		
Project URL	https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/		
EU Project Officer	Christian WILK		

Deliverable	D10.1	Title	Founding principles of the Cloud Governance
Work Package	WP10	Title	Cloud Governance
Submission date	30/05/2025		
Pages	51	Keywords	Founding principles, Governance, Ethics, Implementation principles

Change log

Date	Version	Author	Change
March 2025	0.1	Ad Pollé, Philippe Vendrix, Léna Czech	Redaction of results from work sessions
March-April 2025	1.0	All authors	First draft and subsequent redaction
May 2025	2.0	WP10 participants	Communication to entirety of WP10 for feedback
May 2025	2.1	Xavier Rodier, Louise Gadoin, Léna Czech	Formatting and proofreading

Lead Partner	Europeana (EF)
Responsible Authors	Philippe Vendrix, Léna Czech (CNRS), Ad Pollé (EF), Charlotte Gallini, Rémi Petitcol (FSP), Elisabeth Stadlinger, Christoph Steindl, Anna Pühr (ONB), Elis Marçal (E.C.C.O.), Zoltan Szatucsek (NAH), Sam H. Minelli (META), Aleksandra Nowak (PSNC).
Authors (Partner)	CNRS, EF, FSP, ONB, E.C.C.O., NAH, META, PSNC.
Contributors	Xavier Rodier, Louise Gadoin (CNRS)

Abstract

This document outlines the founding principles of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) governance framework. Developed through collaborative workshops between September 2024 and May 2025, it establishes core values to guide the Cloud's operations as a shared platform for heritage professionals and researchers. The governance structure is built upon seven fundamental principles: **equity**, ensuring fairness in treatment and decision-making; **inclusivity**, guaranteeing diverse stakeholder representation; **awareness**, promoting ethical training and informed decision-making; **transparency**, fostering open processes that build trust; **accountability**, clearly defining responsibilities; **adaptability**, enabling responsive governance to evolving challenges; and **excellence**, maintaining high quality standards across all operations. These principles serve as the ethical foundation for the Cloud's organisational governance, supporting its mission to democratise access to knowledge and digital assets while unifying fragmented communities in the cultural heritage sector. The document further elaborates on implementation strategies across ethical requirements, data sharing infrastructure, operational management, and stakeholder engagement to ensure sustainable and participatory governance.

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Abstract	2
1. Introduction	5
1.1 Scope, structure and methodology.....	5
1.2 Definitions.....	6
1.2.1 Standards.....	6
1.2.2 Principles.....	7
1.2.3 Implementation.....	7
2. Comparing governance principles	7
2.1 Methodology.....	7
2.2 Observations.....	8
2.3 Analysis.....	9
2.3.1 Innovation.....	9
2.3.2 Transparency.....	9
2.3.3 Sustainability.....	9
2.3.4 Inclusivity.....	10
3. Principles of governance	10
3.1 Equity.....	11
3.2 Inclusivity.....	11
3.3 Awareness.....	12
3.4 Transparency.....	12
3.5 Accountability.....	12
3.6 Adaptability.....	13
3.7 Excellence.....	13
4. Implementation of the principles	13
4.1 Ethics.....	13
4.2 Data sharing and infrastructure harmonisation.....	17
4.3 Efficiency.....	19
4.4 Stakeholder engagement.....	20
4.5 Scientific excellence.....	20

Referencesi

Annex.....i

1. Introduction

ECHOES aims to develop and deploy the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH, hereinafter “the Cloud”), a shared platform for heritage professionals and researchers to work with data, innovative scientific and training resources and advanced digital tools co-developed by the heritage community according to their specific needs. To do that, ECHOES will bring together professionals from various disciplines. The fulfilment of ECHOES’ objectives is strongly dependent on enabling collaboration amongst these different disciplines and domains, while empowering users to interact with digital cultural heritage and jointly develop scientific knowledge.

The ECCCH will operate under sustainable conditions and function primarily on a participatory basis requiring transparent and inclusive governance. To achieve this, certain principles driving organisational governance are essential. Without such a clear commitment to such principles, the objective to democratise access to knowledge and digital assets will be put at risk.

1.1 Scope, structure and methodology

The governance principles outlined in this deliverable have been compiled and established as foundational elements for the future Cloud governance framework. Although the Cloud entity itself has not yet been implemented, these principles should be integrated throughout all ongoing ECHOES project activities. Accordingly, these principles have been aligned with the project's overarching objectives and, where applicable, with the specific goals of individual work packages.

The document is structured to provide a clear and logical framework for understanding and implementing governance principles, or standards (see “Definitions” below) for the foundation of the Cloud in relation to the relevant activities within the ECHOES project. It is divided into two distinct sections.

This introductory section positions the document within the broader context of the ECHOES project, offering guidance on its interpretation and practical use. It also details the methodology behind its development, highlighting the collaborative process through which the governance requirements were formulated. Given the diverse backgrounds of the project partners—each representing different perspectives and areas of cultural heritage—it was essential to establish a shared understanding of key concepts.

The founding principles and their implementation constitutes the second - core - part of the document. It is structured around five main chapters, each defining implementation of the founding principles:

- **Ethical** principles – Establishing fundamental ethical principles to guide decision-making, ensuring fairness, transparency, and accountability.
- **Data and infrastructure-related** principles – Addressing the principles of the procedural control on management, sharing, and preservation of the cultural heritage data.
- **Operational** principles – Principles for establishing the governance structures, decision-making processes, and resource management strategies necessary for effective project execution and sustainability.

- Principles for **building a sustainable community** – Focusing on long-term engagement, and stakeholder management.
- Principles of **excellence**

Each principle is presented with a clear explanation for unambiguous interpretation and practical use. Reference codes facilitate their application and enable verification throughout the internal and operational frameworks policies. Where implementations interrelate, cross-references are included to maintain coherence and demonstrate their interdependencies.

This structure provides a comprehensive yet flexible foundation for establishing the governance of the Cloud, supporting both project implementation and long-term sustainability.

The creation of this document was guided by a collaborative process. Between January and March 2025, four dedicated workshops were held, during which core concepts were explored with active participation from various WP members. These sessions fostered a shared understanding and consensus on key governance principles. After the workshops, further discussions took place among different WP leads and members responsible for related areas, ensuring consistency and coherence across the project. The document then underwent several iterative review cycles, during which project partners contributed feedback to refine its content, improve clarity, and ensure alignment with ECHOES' overarching objectives. This iterative, participatory process has resulted in a final document that presents a balanced and comprehensive governance framework.

1.2 Definitions

1.2.1 Standards

The term '*standards*' is used in various contexts and disciplines, including legal, technological, industrial, and organisational frameworks. In general, '*standards*' refer to a set of established – sometimes also de facto – norms that serve as a reference for ensuring consistency, quality, and interoperability in processes, products, or organisational structures.

In this document, the term '*standards*' is used in two specific ways:

- The Cloud governance relies on standards in the broadest sense, including legal regulations, external norms, guidelines, and best practices that provide a recognised framework. These standards may be issued by international organisations, regulatory authorities, cultural heritage communities and serve as a reference point for aligning the Cloud with best practices in its field;
- In addition to external references, '*standards*' is also used to define the set of expectations and commitments that the ECHOES project as the developer of the Cloud establishes for itself. These principles are embodied in internal policies and operational frameworks that ECHOES adheres to for achieving its goal: sustainable access to digital cultural commons.

1.2.2 Principles

Within the framework of Cultural Heritage Cloud governance, ***principles*** refer to fundamental guiding values that ensure responsible, fair, and transparent decision-making processes, the effective running of services, and the support of stakeholders. They provide a basic ethical framework for a normative foundation of research, data governance, and technological applications, shaping policies and practices that balance innovation with social responsibility.

1.2.3 Implementation

Implementation in this document defines structured expectations that translate broader standards and principles into governance provisions, ensuring their effective application within the Cloud's organisational structures. They establish obligations and commitments essential for shaping governance frameworks. Through these *implementations*, the ECHOES project and the Cloud ensure alignment with ethical best practices, regulatory expectations, and strategic objectives for sustainable digital cultural heritage management.

2. Comparing governance principles

2.1 Methodology

Choosing the founding principles for the governance of the Cultural Heritage Cloud is a strategic decision that will have a lasting impact. To establish this list, it appeared important to study what other organisations have done. The aim was to help the ECHOES project choose and define the Cloud's own founding principles for governance, considering its objectives and specificities, as a pan-European digital platform for professional collaboration in the heritage sector.

We created a list of organisations whose area of expertise was of interest for the Cloud (Cultural Heritage or Digital Humanities), as well as organisations with political and governance activities. The aim was to gather material from organisations with similar activities, impact or considerations to ECHOES to learn from their experience and choices.

The list was then further enriched by a call to contributions to ECHOES partners that were invited to provide documents and links to their organisation's governance or ethical principles. The formulation of the call was purposely wide enough to allow partners to share with us any kind of high-level principles – ethical, governing or even professional. We collected the materials in a specific folder in the ECHOES Teams.

The final list, accessible in the Annex, includes a number of European instances such as the European Union and the Council of Europe. Research infrastructures such as DARIAH and E-RIHS also provided interesting insights. Finally, professional organisations, both international and national: European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations (E.C.C.O.), the International Council of Museums (ICOM), the Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland, etc.

2.2 Observations

The process of gathering and comparing principles and values from a range of organisations of various sizes, scopes and fields of expertise has led us to make some methodological and semantic observations. The choice made by the governing body of a given organisation to use words like “principles”, “values”, or “guidelines” can be very telling. Indeed, although these terms can have similar meanings, they should not be understood as interchangeable in the wider context of this document¹. Each term reflects not only a different semantic register but also a distinct disciplinary orientation and institutional intention.

The choice of wording signals how an organisation conceives of its own authority, audience, and methodological commitments. For example, invoking “principles” often suggests a foundation of universal or enduring norms², while “values” implies some element of relativity or subjectivity³, and typically reflect internal cultural priorities or shared aspirations. Similarly, a “code of conduct” tends to imply enforceable standards tied to professional accountability⁴, whereas “guidelines” may allow for broader interpretative flexibility⁵.

One area where this specificity becomes particularly salient is in the formulation of professional codes of conduct. Unlike more abstract or aspirational declarations of values, these codes serve as concrete operational tools. They articulate expected behaviours, delineate responsibilities, and often include mechanisms for accountability. Their function is not merely symbolic — they support professional identity, reinforce institutional integrity, and can serve as a bridge between ethical intention and practice.

The study of the codes of conduct gathered in the Annex might seem a bit of a stretch from the objective of this document. However, we chose to include them in our comparative exercise as at least part of them reflect broader governance and ethical principles. It appeared important to understand and include the broader professional considerations of some of the communities that will constitute the user base of the future Cloud. These codes have, as a result, partly informed the section 4 on Implementations of the Founding Principles.

Mapping these documents across institutions sometimes proved challenging. Some organisations do not present such frameworks in a formalised or consolidated form. While their values or ethical commitments may be discernible through strategic plans, mission statements, or governance documents, they are not always codified as standalone lists or policies. Nevertheless, when they do

¹ However, in this section “values”, “principles”, “guidelines” and codes of conduct will be analysed together to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the choices made by the organisations studied.

² “Principle”, Oxford English Dictionary, Oxford University Press, 2025.
URL: https://www.oed.com/dictionary/principle_n?tab=meaning_and_use#28387145

³ “Value”, Merriam-Webster Dictionary, Merriam-Webster, 2025. URL: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/value>.

⁴ “Code of conduct”, in “Code”, Oxford English Dictionary, Oxford University Press, 2025.
URL: https://www.oed.com/dictionary/code_n?tab=meaning_and_use#1284443290.

⁵ “Guideline”, Merriam-Webster Dictionary, Merriam-Webster, 2025. URL: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/guideline>

exist, they are generally accessible—often published in dedicated sections of institutional websites under headings such as “Our Mission,” “Our Values,” or “Strategic focus or plans,”⁶. The variance in both form and terminology underscores not only differences in organisational culture but also broader methodological and political choices regarding how norms are articulated and enacted.

2.3 Analysis

Some principles or values seem to be quite widely shared by a very wide range of organisations, independent of their scope (international, European or national) and area of expertise (cultural heritage, digital humanities, politics, etc.). Although the word chosen to summarise one of these principles might differ slightly, the more in-depth description that usually comes with it demonstrates its closeness to others. These common principles or values appear to be unavoidable as they lay the basis for fair governance and a long-term vision. The four most referenced principles appear to be Innovation, Transparency, Sustainability and Inclusivity⁷.

2.3.1 Innovation

Innovation stands out as a guiding principle that signals a forward-thinking governance style. The institutions that refer to Innovation usually imply or explicitly refer to agile, adaptive governance practices that support experimentation and continuous improvement. The organisations that refer to these principles cover various fields of expertise such as digital humanities (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities - DARIAH), heritage science (the European Infrastructure for Heritage Science - E-RIHS), digital infrastructures (European Data Space) and even wider political governance (Council of Europe).

2.3.2 Transparency

Transparency remains a cornerstone of ethical governance, closely associated with accountability and public trust. It can also refer to democratic decision-making, open communication and access to information (International Council on Monuments and Sites – ICOMOS). However, it does not automatically imply complete democratic participation in all matters. Some limitations and smaller decisional instances are acceptable as long as they do not prevent accountability. Again, very diverse organisations share this principle: the Council of Europe, the European Data Space and a national training institution – the Fondazione Scuola dei beni e delle attività culturali.

2.3.3 Sustainability

Sustainability can be understood as a relatively large principle. Based on our comparative table, it seems to encompass environmental sustainability and impact monitoring, as well as economic,

⁶ See for example ICOMOS (“Our Missions and Values”), Europeana (“Mission”), NEMO (“Strategic focus”), ICOM (“Strategic Plan”).

⁷ By “most common principles or values” we mean the principles whose name or description are the most referenced in the comparative table in Annexe 1. The linking of the description of principles made by the referenced organisations contains an element of subjectivity as it is the authors’ interpretation.

technological and even governance sustainability to some extent. Technological and governance sustainability also imply adaptability, which has several occurrences as well. Sustainability is shared by several international and multidisciplinary organisations such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), DARIAH, the Network of European Museum Organisations (NEMO) and the European Data Space. EOSC, DARIAH and the European Data Space also share a specific area of expertise that currently raises a lot of questions relating to sustainability: digital tools infrastructure, and particularly Clouds of data spaces.

Finally, sustainability can also be understood as touching upon social considerations about the social and societal impact of an organisation on society and some communities. NEMO, E.C.C.O. and the Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland include such considerations.

2.3.4 Inclusivity

Inclusivity and principles or values closely associated are the most widely shared. They apply to all the types of organisations studied and contribute to preventing any kind of abuse or discrimination against the people involved in or covered by the organisation. DARIAH, the Heritage Council of Ireland and the Institute for Archaeologists share such a principle. It relates to complementary values or principles like Equality (the European Union) and Solidarity (ICOMOS). However, Inclusivity can entail wider considerations regarding the inclusion of specific scientific disciplines within the scope of an organisation. Finally, it can be linked to collaboration (International Council of Museums – ICOM).

The selection of principles by various organisations and institutions is both insightful and indicative of their specific objectives and priorities, shaped by their respective needs and scopes. These principles often respond to sector-specific demands, guide professional practice, support long-term strategic planning within the heritage sector, and articulate each entity's mission and interests. The choices made reflect the unique characteristics of institutions operating in the cultural heritage and/or digital sectors.

Regarding organisations whose activities focus on either cultural heritage, science or digital humanities, the chosen principles appear to contribute to forging governance frameworks that are both resilient and responsive, capable of balancing technological ambition with ethical stewardship of research and cultural heritage protection in Europe. ECHOES has striven to achieve this delicate balance by selecting the principles presented in the following section.

3. Principles of governance

As the Cultural Heritage Cloud is an initiative whose objectives are to democratise the access to knowledge and digital assets and to unify fragmented communities, it shall operate under strict sustainability conditions and function primarily on a participatory basis. Thus, a transparent and inclusive governance system is necessary. To achieve this, the definition of core values, to be interpreted as the principles driving the Cloud's organisational governance, is essential.

The efforts to define such principles - or ethical prerequisites for organisational governance - should not be understood as defining the practical or logistical functioning of decision-making bodies within the Cloud quite yet. However, they will be integral to the construction of the governance, as they represent its moral and ethical foundation. They do not specifically address data governance principles, such as legal compliance or access and reuse policies, as these principles will be defined and expanded upon in the Cloud's Data Management Plan.

Additionally, these principles do not prevail over a strong commitment to respect legal obligations. On the contrary, they are built upon the legal obligations in order to establish an even stronger engagement towards certain values for the Cloud. Indeed, the Cloud commits to respecting fundamental rights throughout all its activities, including in organisational governance and decision-making. In the context of the Cloud, certain fundamental rights - as protected under the European Charter of Fundamental Rights - are particularly essential, namely the freedom of expression and information (art. 11), and the freedom of the arts and sciences (art. 13).

Overall, these fundamental principles are directed at those participating in the Cloud, so that anyone participating in the governance processes shall commit to respect them, and anyone engaging with the platform and the tools it offers shall benefit from the ethical protection they afford. This third part is thus destined to list and define these principles. Their implementation, which may take different forms depending on the shape and composition of the governance structure of the Cloud, will be the subject of a fourth part in this document.

The seven principles go as follows:

3.1 Equity

The Cultural Heritage Cloud commits to maintaining high standards of equity. This must be understood as ensuring fairness in the way people are treated, both in everyday activities and decision-making processes and structures. In application of the principle of equity, policies and decisions shall not unfairly benefit certain groups or serve personal interests.

Thus, no decision concerning the Cloud shall be taken without considering the potential consequences on the equitable environment we aim to create. If a decision is likely to create or exacerbate any inequities in the community, measures will be taken to mitigate the risks, and adequate processes will be put in place to correct any lingering negative repercussions.

3.2 Inclusivity

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is destined to be used by a large variety of actors in many sectors, and to safeguard a diversity of methodologies, practices, skills, and workflows. In consequence, inclusivity is key to achieving the project's objectives, and it strives to ensure that all its processes and activities include relevant participants and stakeholders. As a fundamental principle, inclusivity should particularly be reflected in the composition of all the governance bodies. This requires a clear understanding of the relevant actors in the project and of the stakes of their work. On that basis, the

Cultural Heritage Cloud shall ensure that the composition of its governance bodies is selected or elected based on a democratic process. Such a process should be made transparent and participatory, fostering an environment where all voices are heard.

While maintaining stability to the highest extent possible, a regular renewal of membership shall be considered to ensure that diverse views are adequately reflected in the governance of the Cloud. In addition to this, the Cloud shall strive to continuously assess and evaluate the measures adopted and the composition of governance bodies and communities to improve on their diversity.

3.3 Awareness

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is committed to ensuring that the actions and behaviours of decision-makers within its governance structure adhere to the ethical principles defined here. To achieve this, it is essential that individuals involved in governance are thoroughly trained in ethics management. Such training fosters the integrity and reliability of decisions and activities within the Cloud.

Accordingly, the Cloud should take proactive responsibility for implementing these training initiatives. Ethical guidelines, case studies, and scenario-based learning should be developed to enhance ethical reasoning skills. Furthermore, the Cultural Heritage Cloud must ensure that decision-makers remain informed about applicable legal provisions and codes of conduct beyond ethical principles. In addition to keeping stakeholders informed, the Cloud's governance bodies should assess situations where stakeholder involvement in decision-making is appropriate and establish processes and structures to facilitate such participation.

3.4 Transparency

Sustaining the Cultural Heritage Cloud environment also, and perhaps most importantly, requires that trust is built among stakeholders and users alike. An important tool in building trust in a community is transparency; and a transparent Cloud calls for clear and accessible decision-making processes.

Transparency means that all actions, policies, and decisions are conducted in an open manner, allowing stakeholders to understand how and why decisions are made. It involves actively sharing information, ensuring that data and documents are readily available, and fostering an environment where oversight and participation are encouraged.

3.5 Accountability

In addition to transparency, accountability is also a powerful tool to build trust in the Cultural Heritage Cloud's community, as it prevents potential misunderstandings. Accountability in the Cloud's governance ensures that all decision-making and managing bodies are answerable for their actions, fostering responsibility, fairness, and effective management.

This principle involves clearly defining roles and responsibilities, ensuring that those in positions of authority are held responsible for their decisions and actions. Accountability requires mechanisms to evaluate performance, address failures, and uphold ethical standards.

3.6 Adaptability

The Cultural Heritage Cloud's governance is founded on the principle of adaptability, ensuring that governance practices are robust, forward-thinking, and capable of addressing evolving challenges. It begins with a proactive approach to identifying and mitigating ethical risks. This involves recognising potential ethical dilemmas and conflicts of interest, developing strategies to address these risks effectively, and implementing strong whistle-blower protection mechanisms to safeguard transparency and accountability. Regular ethical risk assessments are conducted to anticipate and manage potential issues before they escalate.

Adaptability is a cornerstone of Cloud governance. Policies are designed to be sufficiently flexible to adapt to future changes in ethical norms and technological advancements. This flexibility is achieved by fostering a culture of innovation and continuous improvement, implementing decision-making processes that can quickly respond to new information, and regularly reviewing governance structures to ensure they remain relevant and effective. Learning from both successes and failures is encouraged, allowing governance approaches to evolve dynamically based on experience.

3.7 Excellence

Just as the stakeholders and users of the Cultural Heritage Cloud expect excellence in the services and tools that will be offered to them, it is important that the governance of the Cloud is held to the same standard of quality. In terms of governance, excellence is not a fixed target but rather an ever-evolving objective: to ensure that the instances of governance are always efficient, work at the best of their capacity, and take sensible and sound decisions. By making a promise of excellence, the members and bodies of governance commit themselves to meeting the expectations of those they serve: the users of the Cloud.

This final principle truly ties all the preceding together: it guarantees that there will be no excellence without equity and inclusivity; transparency promotes excellence by allowing the users to follow the decision-making process and ensure that their needs and requirements are considered at every step; and if the governance instances fail to meet the quality standards that are expected of them, they can be held accountable.

4. Implementation of the principles

4.1 Ethics

ID	REQUIREMENT	IMPLEMENTATION
----	-------------	----------------

E.01	The Cloud shall uphold high standards of equity by ensuring that decision-making processes and structures are fair, impartial, and do not unjustly benefit specific groups or personal interests over others.	<p>The Cloud commits to maintaining high standards of equity, understood as ensuring fairness or justice in the way people are treated in activities and decision-making processes and structures. This should result in policies and decisions not unfairly benefiting certain groups or personal interests over others.</p> <p>To ensure this, decision-making for the Cloud shall always consider whether decisions will ultimately lead to a more equitable environment, and whether they will create or exacerbate inequities. If the latter is answered positively, measures will be taken to mitigate such risks, and processes will be put in place for correcting inequities.</p> <p>Furthermore, to safeguard equity, the Cloud commits to implementing policies that promote fair and transparent decision-making processes and participation mechanisms and to conducting regular audits to identify and address disparities in outcomes.</p> <p>The principle of equity is reflected across multiple objectives within the ECHOES project and the Cloud, ensuring fair governance, inclusive participation, and equal access to resources. The establishment of long-term governance and compliance monitoring preventing unfair advantages in decision-making processes. Equity is also embedded in dissemination efforts, ensuring that professionals, institutions, and the public have equal opportunities to engage with and benefit from the Cloud.</p>
E.02	The Cloud shall ensure inclusivity in its governance by establishing election processes for governance bodies and communities, regularly assessing their composition to reflect diverse perspectives maintaining stability.	<p>The Cloud strives to ensure that all its processes and activities include relevant participants and stakeholders. Given the importance for the Cloud to safeguard a diversity of methodologies, practices, skills, and workflows, inclusivity is key to achieving the project's objectives.</p> <p>Inclusivity should be reflected in the composition of all its governance bodies and communities, ensuring gender equality and equitable access for early-career researchers.</p> <p>ECHOES shall ensure inclusivity in its governance by establishing election processes for governance bodies by regularly assessing their composition to reflect its communities, diverse perspectives and maintaining stability. Such processes should be transparent and participatory, fostering an environment where multiple voices are heard and represented.</p> <p>In addition, the Cloud shall strive to continuously assess and evaluate the measures adopted and the composition of governance bodies and its communities to enhance diversity, strengthen gender balance, and ensure fair opportunities for emerging scholars to engage in decision-making processes.</p> <p>The Cloud integrates inclusivity by ensuring diverse participation in governance and engagement activities. The governance framework promotes equitable representation and democratic decision-making, ensuring opportunities for early-career researchers and underrepresented groups.</p> <p>The principle of inclusivity is reflected in the objectives related to the Communication strategy actively involves a broad range of stakeholders, fostering awareness and accessibility. Additionally, the Cascading Grants Programme directly supports diversity by engaging cultural heritage institutions with limited representation. The commitment to engaging a diverse range of cultural heritage institutions and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration supports also this principle by considering multiple perspectives in the project's development.</p>
E.03	The Cloud shall uphold fundamental rights in alignment with the European Charter of	The Cloud commits to respecting fundamental rights throughout all of its activities, including in organisational governance decision-making. In the context of the Cloud, certain fundamental rights are particularly essential,

	Fundamental Rights within the ECCCH.	<p>namely Freedom of expression and information (article 11 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights), and Freedom of the arts and sciences (article 13 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights).</p> <p>Open communication and dissemination guarantee broad access to knowledge, supporting the unrestricted exchange of information. Actively engaging cultural heritage professionals, academic researchers, decision-makers, and the public fosters a participatory environment where scholarly contributions are valued. Encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration strengthens academic freedom by enabling diverse research approaches and cross-field dialogue.</p>
E.04	The Cloud is committed to maintaining the highest scientific ethical standards and promoting Open Science principles.	<p>Scientific integrity relies on ethical research practices, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and responsible data-sharing. the Cloud governance will align with Open Science principles, promoting open access to research outputs, methodologies, and datasets while maintaining ethical safeguards. The project will encourage FAIR principles, facilitating structured, well-documented, and ethically sound data-sharing without imposing mandatory open access. Governance policies will define clear guidelines for responsible authorship, data citation, and ethical publication practices, ensuring contributors retain control over their research while enabling broader knowledge dissemination.</p> <p>The governance transition to a legal entity will embed these principles into long-term research management, ensuring sustainability. The dissemination of the Cloud outcomes will ensure that research findings are shared ethically with professionals, institutions, and the public. Additionally, interdisciplinary collaboration will strengthen ethical research methodologies by fostering responsible data-sharing practices across diverse scientific communities. The curation of the Knowledge Base will further ensure that scientific data is systematically preserved and made accessible in alignment with ethical and FAIR principles.</p>
E.05	The Cloud shall maintain transparency in all governance activities and ensure accountability through structured oversight mechanisms.	<p>Transparency and accountability are essential for ethical governance, requiring clear documentation, open decision-making, and independent oversight. the Cloud will establish mechanisms for publishing governance decisions, ensuring that stakeholders have access to relevant information. Regular audits and evaluation reports will provide accountability, allowing corrective measures to be taken when necessary.</p> <p>The long-term governance framework will integrate transparency as a fundamental principle. Compliance monitoring will ensure that governance structures remain accountable, while structured evaluation and reporting will provide continuous oversight of governance decisions.</p>
E.06	The Cloud governance shall ensure the protection of personal and sensitive data , adhering to strict European privacy regulations and fundamental ethical principles.	<p>Respecting privacy is essential for both research data governance within the Cloud and the broader organisational and operational aspects of the Cloud. The governance framework must ensure that all personal, institutional, and operational data is collected, stored, and processed securely. Policies will be in place to enforce data minimisation, limiting the collection and retention of unnecessary information. Furthermore, privacy impact assessments will be conducted regularly to identify risks and strengthen protective measures.</p> <p>Governance mechanisms will ensure compliance with relevant data protection regulations, including GDPR, providing oversight for both technical and organisational privacy concerns. The CH knowledge base will incorporate privacy-preserving mechanisms, enforcing privacy considerations when sharing information with stakeholders, ensuring that personal and institutional data is handled responsibly in all public and internal communications.</p>

E.07	The Cloud shall ensure that intellectual property rights (IPR) align with ethical best practices, protecting authors' rights.	<p>Respecting intellectual property rights is crucial in research and cultural heritage governance. the Cloud will establish clear policies for licensing data. Contributors will be recognised for their intellectual contributions, and mechanisms will be put in place to balance proprietary rights with Open Science commitments.</p> <p>Governance structures will integrate IPR protections, ensuring that all stakeholders' rights are respected. The CH knowledge base will implement secure access mechanisms, balancing openness with IPR protection. Additionally, community engagement strategies will ensure that intellectual contributions from diverse stakeholders are respected and acknowledged.</p>
E.08	The Cloud shall recognise and uphold the control of ownership rights of individual, and institutional researchers, contributors, and their communities over their data an intellectual property.	<p>Respecting data ownership is also fundamental to the ethical framework for the distributed data services, ensuring that those who generate, collect, or contribute data maintain control over its use. The Cloud will establish clear policies on data ownership, including consent-based data sharing, clear declarations, proper attribution, and secure data storage. These policies will protect individuals and institutions from unauthorised use and misuse while promoting responsible data collaboration. Mechanisms will be in place to address disputes and ensure that stakeholders retain appropriate control over their data.</p> <p>To reinforce these principles, the Cloud will integrate data ownership safeguards into its dissemination efforts, ensuring that contributors retain proper recognition when research outputs are shared with professionals, institutions, and the public. The curation of the Knowledge Base will ensure that data ownership rights are respected in structured information management, promoting responsible attribution and ethical data reuse.</p>
E.09	The Cloud shall ensure the transparency of AI applications , that they are ethically designed and aligned with principles of fairness and accountability.	<p>AI technologies must adhere to ethical governance frameworks to prevent bias, enhance transparency, and ensure accountability. the Cloud will establish AI governance policies that align with the EU AI Act's risk-based classification.</p> <p>High-risk AI applications within the project will be subject to strict oversight, requiring inclusivity audits, explainability measures, and mechanisms for human oversight. This is particularly relevant for AI-generated synthetic voices and visual reconstructions of persons, where AI models could generate ethically questionable content or for AI applications processing personal data from archival collections. For lower-risk AI applications, such as automated language translation tools or text-based metadata tagging, the Cloud governance will require transparency obligations, ensuring that users are informed when AI is in use. These applications will also undergo periodic evaluation to ensure that they do not introduce biases or inaccuracies that could impact accessibility and inclusivity.</p> <p>Limited-risk AI applications will be designed with safeguards that promote responsible and transparent use. To ensure compliance with these standards, the Cloud will implement an AI Risk Register to classify and monitor AI systems based on their risk category.</p> <p>The Cloud governance will integrate ethical AI policies into decision-making processes to ensure responsible development and deployment. Interdisciplinary collaboration will support the evaluation of AI fairness by incorporating diverse disciplinary perspectives. Evaluation tools will include specific mechanisms for monitoring AI-driven processes, ensuring they comply with ethical standards.</p>
E.10	The Cloud shall apply environmental sustainability perspectives in its governance and	Governance plays a critical role in ensuring environmental sustainability by establishing policies that promote responsible resource use and mitigate environmental impact. The Cloud governance will enforce sustainability

	operational practices, encouraging and supporting measures to minimise its ecological footprint.	standards while supporting initiatives that reduce the project's ecological footprint. This includes prioritising energy-efficient digital infrastructure, sustainable procurement practices, and environmentally conscious operational policies. Long-term governance planning will integrate sustainability as a core value. The CH Cloud infrastructure will be designed with energy efficiency in mind, ensuring that digital resources are managed sustainably. Additionally, interdisciplinary collaboration will support research into sustainable cultural heritage practices, ensuring that environmental considerations are embedded in heritage preservation strategies.
E.11	The Cloud shall ensure that its governance framework ensures resilience and adaptability to the evolving ethical challenges while maintaining core ethical principles.	Ethical governance must be able to adapt to emerging challenges while ensuring that fundamental principles are upheld. The Cloud will implement a governance model that enables adjustments in response to new ethical concerns, technological advancements, or stakeholder needs. Regular ethical risk assessments will be conducted to identify areas requiring adaptation, and structured feedback mechanisms will be established to facilitate responsive governance. This approach is integrated into the long-term governance and management of the project, ensuring that ethical principles remain embedded in decision-making processes. Compliance monitoring will allow for ongoing assessment of ethical risks and necessary adjustments. The engagement of a diverse range of cultural heritage institutions will further enhance ethical resilience by incorporating multiple perspectives into governance decisions.
E.12	The Cloud shall provide decision-makers with regular capacity building actions to enhance their ability in applying ethical principles in practice.	The Cloud strives to ensure that the actions and behaviours of decision-makers within the governance of the Cloud follows ethical principles. For this to be possible, decision-makers in the relevant governance bodies should be well-trained in ethics management . This will safeguard the integrity and trustworthiness of decisions and activities within the Cloud. The Cloud should take responsibility for ensuring that such training efforts are put in place. This includes facilitating regular workshops on ethical principles and their application on governance. This should happen alongside the creation of ethical guidelines, as well as case studies and scenario-based learning to develop ethical reasoning skills. Establishing structured long-term governance requires equipping leaders with ethical reasoning skills, reinforcing responsible decision-making. To maintain compliance with commitments, ethics training provides decision-makers with the necessary tools to apply ethical principles in governance oversight and accountability measures. As the project transitions to a legal entity, embedding ethical guidelines and structured training within its governance ensures that transparency and trustworthiness remain fundamental principles.

4.2 Data sharing and infrastructure harmonisation

ID	REQUIREMENT	IMPLEMENTATION
----	-------------	----------------

D.01	The Cloud shall provide and apply a data management strategy based on the founding principles.	The Cloud will manage heterogeneous data from diverse cultural heritage institutions, enterprises and individual professionals, ensuring interoperability through standard metadata models and compliance with international governance frameworks. Thus, the project guarantees sustainable data management and will work out a detailed data management plan for the collaborative Cloud. The data management plan must implement the FAIR principles and requires detailed information on the subsequent use of the data. A clearly defined data management policy is the basis for the reuse of data and, therefore, for derived data sharing and data access policies.
D.02	The Cloud shall include scenarios for data distribution and data integration based on international standards.	The Cloud must integrate into existing research infrastructures. The application of international data standards/formats and thesauri ensures interoperability with other external entities. To achieve this, the data must be publicly accessible, and ECHOES must be able to guarantee this access during project runtime and beyond. The application of international data governance standards includes the use of interoperable and standardised data formats for data and metadata. External entities are independent of the project. This also applies to entities funded by ECHOES through the Cascading Grants program.
D.03	The Cloud shall adopt and/or establish security policies and guidelines in alignment with the ISO/IEC 27000 series.	The Cloud works with data from various individuals and institutions. It must guarantee to never pose a security risk to external or internal persons nor institutions. The project will therefore develop comprehensive security policies and guidelines regarding data management, cybersecurity, and software development in general. Key international standards for information security management systems, such as the ISO/IEC 27000 series, will be considered in the development of the policies. It must be ensured that unauthorised access to data is not possible, which could result in data being intercepted, manipulated, or deleted; that it is not possible to misuse identities in the system for unethical and illegal purposes; and that the integrity and provenance of the data are guaranteed at all times. Furthermore, the Cloud must be compliant with the GDPR when storing personal data to minimise potential security risks. External entities shall be selected with reference to the EU Cloud Code of Conduct to ensure alignment with GDPR-compliant data protection standards.
D.04	The Cloud shall provide sustainability in access, preservation, and integrity of data.	The Cloud must foresee sustainable infrastructure and results regarding long-term data access and preservation. It must be ensured that these achievements use data formats which are compliant with long-term archiving standards (e.g. ISO 14721) as well as long-term archiving infrastructure (e.g. certified repositories), which are available independent from the ECHOES project duration, and which can be migrated to other systems. The sustainability strategy must contain a consistent data lifecycle that guarantees data integrity for all assets. This includes a detailed change management for editorial tasks as well as archival obligations (e.g. retention and deletion policies).
D.05	The Cloud shall ensure reversibility regarding data, processes and mechanisms within the governance framework.	The Cloud shall ensure the ability to reverse decisions , processes, or changes when deemed necessary to protect the integrity, accessibility, and sustainability of cultural heritage data/information. This includes the capability to rollback software updates, restore previous states of datasets using systematic data versioning methods, and revoke governance decisions if they prove harmful or ineffective. Mechanisms for implementing reversibility must be documented, tested regularly, and incorporated into the broader governance framework to ensure transparency and accountability.

4.3 Efficiency

ID	REQUIREMENT	IMPLEMENTATION
F.01	The Cloud shall ensure transparency in its governance structure : once the various instances of the Cloud governance are established, their structure shall be made available to the public.	<p>Publishing clear governance diagram(s) is essential for the users of the Cloud to understand the roles and objectives of the different governance instances, as well as the interactions between them.</p> <p>In addition, publishing the names of the people involved in the various instances helps build trust within the community, and keeps the feeling of an impersonal, arbitrary governance at bay.</p>
F.02	The Cloud will also ensure transparency in decision-making : in order to have an efficient and transparent Cloud governance, it shall ensure that users of the Cloud can easily find clear and detailed information on important decision processes.	Decisions, especially those affecting users and their data, shall be traceable to a specific decision-making process and to the relevant instances.
F.03	The Cloud shall establish a clear communication on decisions . Important decisions shall be made public.	<p>Any decisions taken by governance instances that have the potential to affect the user experience of the Cloud, or any decisions that relate to the management of data must be made public before the expected date of implementation.</p> <p>Keeping the users of the Cloud informed is crucial to establish a lasting and involved community, and to create trust.</p>
F.04	A process for appeal of decisions will be implemented within the Cloud.	A decision may be appealed by one or several stakeholders, provided they prove the decisions is detrimental to their interests.
F.05	The Cloud shall have precise documenting and reporting workflows. Diligent reports of instances meeting must be written and archived in order to document the decision-making processes.	<p>Internal reporting within the governance instances of the Cloud is necessary to ensure fluidity in the working processes, and accountability.</p> <p>It is also essential in the event of an audit by an authority providing funding (either European, national or local), to be able to present proof of the actions undertaken and the decisions made.</p>
F.06	The Cloud shall ensure its own budget sustainability : a mid-to long-term plan of budget use shall be drafted by the competent governance instances to ensure medium-term budget sustainability and be presented to the stakeholders for validation.	<p>To ensure the sustainability of the budget of the Cloud, the use of the budget should be planned in the short, medium and long term.</p> <p>Presenting a medium-term budget plan to the stakeholders ensures that a satisfactory balance is found in the division of financial resources and increases accountability for the governance instances.</p> <p>In the event of significant financial losses, the relevant governance instances shall present the stakeholders with a plan to stop the losses and limit the consequences on the functioning of the Cloud.</p>

4.4 Stakeholder engagement

ID	REQUIREMENT	IMPLEMENTATION
S.01	The Cloud shall ensure that mechanisms for user feedback incorporation are put in place.	The Cloud must be able to adapt to the needs and practices of its users. It shall therefore design and implement mechanisms within the governance that enable the gathering of user feedback and its incorporation. The project will thus guarantee the adaptability, responsiveness and sustainability of the Cloud by remaining up to date with the users' needs.
S.04	The Cloud shall ensure transparency in collaboration and decision-making with stakeholders.	The governance of the Cloud should enable transparent relations with stakeholders. It should guarantee that all processes and decisions are clearly documented and openly communicated to ensure trust among stakeholders. This shall be achieved by establishing clear lines of responsibility and authority, implementing mechanisms for stakeholders to question and challenge decisions, ensuring consequences for misconduct or failure to meet obligations and scheduling regular reporting on performance and goal achievement.
S.02	The governance model of the Cloud shall ensure customisation and adaptability of services through continuous stakeholder engagement .	The Cloud shall design and apply clear, stakeholder-informed metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of the Cloud services. These metrics must be developed in consultation with end users and updated through continuous stakeholder feedback. Regular tracking and reporting shall ensure high standards of data quality, system performance, and compliance. The inclusion of stakeholder input in service evaluation will support the ongoing customisation and adaptability of the Cloud, ensuring its flexibility, relevance, and long-term sustainability.
S.03	The Cloud shall support the continuous improvement and innovation .	Governance must support the ability to quickly adapt the environment to changes such as technological advances or regulatory changes, ensuring that the governance remains reactive. It should encourage the adoption of new technologies and approaches to continuously improve operational processes and adapt to future challenges. Identify, assess, and mitigate risks proactively to avoid operational disruptions and ensure stability.

4.5 Scientific excellence

ID	REQUIREMENT	IMPLEMENTATION
X.01	The Cloud shall ensure scientific rigour in the development of tools, services, and methodologies for digital cultural heritage.	To ensure the highest standards of scientific and professional excellence, all components of the Cloud shall be subject to rigorous evaluation mechanisms, including interdisciplinary peer review, technical validation, and user testing. Governance policies must institutionalise continuous improvement processes that incorporate structured feedback from the heritage community, fostering innovation, relevance, and sustained excellence in all project outcomes.
X.02	The governance model of the Cloud shall institutionalise cross-disciplinary co-creation as a core mechanism for ensuring scientific and professional excellence.	The governance framework must formally integrate co-creation processes involving researchers, heritage professionals, and technologists. It shall ensure that decision-making bodies and working groups reflect disciplinary diversity and are empowered to guide the iterative development of tools, services, and methods tailored to sector-specific needs. Governance rules must also support structured knowledge exchange and the systematic inclusion of humanities, social sciences, and technological expertise in all strategic and operational layers of the Cloud.
X.03	The governance model of the Cloud shall enable excellence through strategic collaboration	Governance policies shall mandate alignment and formal cooperation with established European and international research infrastructures (e.g., EOSC, DARIAH, Europeana) to ensure complementarity, knowledge transfer, and best practice adoption. This strategic engagement will reinforce the excellence and interoperability of the Cloud services and datasets.

	with leading research infrastructures.	
X. 04	The Cloud shall promote excellence through training and capacity-building NG across the cultural heritage sector.	Governance policies shall require the development and maintenance of high-quality training programmes co-created with stakeholders to strengthen competencies in digital tools, data literacy, and interdisciplinary research. To foster excellence across all levels of the heritage sector, these programmes must include open educational resources and modular, adaptable learning paths accessible to institutions of varying size and capacity.

References

ALLEA (2023), The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. Berlin. DOI 10.26356/ECOC.

Archaeological Institute of America, Code of Professional Standards, approved by the Council on December 29, 1994, amended December 29, 1997 and January 5, 2008.

Code of Conduct for Cloud Service Providers : Lignes directrices pour la protection des données et la transparence : <https://www.edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2024-02/eucloudcoc.pdf>

Council of Europe, “12 Principles of Good Democratic Governance ». URL: [https://www.coe.int/en/web/centre-of-expertise-for-multilevel-governance/12-principles#{%2225565951%22:\[0\]}](https://www.coe.int/en/web/centre-of-expertise-for-multilevel-governance/12-principles#{%2225565951%22:[0]}).

DARIAH 2020: 25 Key Actions for a Stronger DARIAH by 2020, a “living document” that has been approved by the DARIAH’s General Assembly in November 2017.

[Data management - H2020 Online Manual](#)

[Data principles - Digital Society](#)

E-RIHS ERIC, Scientific and Technical Description, v 5.02, 2022 (internal document, not public yet).

Ethics and data protection https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf

European Association of Archaeologists, The EAA Code of Practice, approved on 27 September 1997, amended on 19 September 2009.

European Cloud Alliance : <https://www.europeancloudalliance.com/>

European *Cloud Initiative* : Création d'une économie des données compétitive et sécurisée : <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/european-cloud-initiative/report?sid=8501>

European Commission, , “1.4 Principles”. JRC Data Spaces Knowledge Base. URL: <https://wikis.ec.europa.eu/spaces/jrcdataspaceswiki/pages/57444509/1.4+Principles>.

European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers’ Organisations, E.C.C.O. Professional Guidelines (II), adopted by E.C.C.O.’s General Assembly on 7 March 2003.

European Data Space, URL: <https://wikis.ec.europa.eu/spaces/jrcdataspaceswiki/pages/57444509/1.4+Principles>.

European Interoperability Framework: https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf

European Open Science Cloud, EOSC Declaration, Brussels, 26 October 2017.

European Strategy for Data : Recommandations sur la gouvernance des données : <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>

European Union, “Aims and Values”. URL: https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/principles-and-values/aims-and-values_en.

Europeana, “Mission”. URL: <https://pro.europeana.eu/about-us/mission>.

Fondazione Scuola dei Beni e delle Attività Culturali, Codice etico e di comportamento, approvato dal Consiglio di Gestione in data di 4 febbraio 2019.

[Guidelines for the preservation of digital heritage - UNESCO Digital Library](#)

Guidelines on cloud computing services for the European banking sector : Lignes directrices éthiques et de gouvernance:

https://www.bankingsupervision.europa.eu/legalframework/publiccons/pdf/ssm.pubcon240603_draftguide.en.pdf

Heritage Council of Ireland, Our Place in Time, Heritage Council Strategic Plan 2023-2028.

Historic Environment Scotland, Policy Statement, 2016.

ICOMOS, “Our missions and values”. URL: <https://www.icomos.org/icomos-our-mission-and-values/>.

Institute of Archaeologists, Code of Conduct, ratified and adopted on 3 June 1985 revised on 12 September 1988, 17 September 1993, 14 October 1994, 22 September 1995, 11 September 1996, 10 September 1997, 7 September 2000, 5 September 2002, 2 October 2006, 1 October 2007, 15 October 2008, 12 October 2009 and 14 April 2010.

International Council of Museums, ICOM Code of Ethics for Museums, 2017.

International Council of Museums, Strategic Plan 2022-2028, 2022.

Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Global Change, Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2020, 2020.

NEMO, “Strategic focus”. URL: <https://www.ne-mo.org/about-us/our-strategy/strategic-focus/>.

Pascal Lievaux, Isabelle Pallot-Frossard (Dir.), Un patrimoine pour l’avenir, une science pour le patrimoine. Une aventure européenne de la recherche et de l’innovation. 2022. hal-03796130.

[Principles for Digital Development](#)

Règlement général sur la protection des données (**RGPD**) : Dispositions pour la gouvernance éthique des données: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/FR/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>

Robert SHIPLEY, Jason F. KOVACS, “Good governance principles for the cultural heritage sector: lessons from international experience”, Corporate Governance, Vol. 8 No. 2, Emerald Group Publishing Ltd, 2008, pp. 214-228. URL:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/238325099_Good_governance_principles_for_the_cultural_heritage_sector_Lessons_from_international_experience

Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland, Code of Professional Conduct, 2009.

The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure <https://openscholarlyinfrastructure.org/>

Theo LYNN & al., Data privacy and trust in cloud computing, Palgrave, 2021

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1w3NIedCJKsHTsw7pg5bAUOAUIlljkZKr>

Todd PRESNER, Ethics of the algorithm, Princeton, 2024

(<https://press.princeton.edu/books/hardcover/9780691258966/ethics-of-the-algorithm>)

[Turning FAIR into reality - Publications Office of the EU](#)

[UNESCO Charter on the Preservation of the Digital Heritage](#)

[What are the 7 main principles of GDPR?](#)

Annex

This table gathers the values and principles of a very wide range of institutions whose scopes include international governance, cultural heritage governance or management, digital governance or management. We made the decision to include them all, without restricting our choice to governance values or principles as this list has also provided the ECHOES project with interesting insight regarding implementation principles as well. It will also provide an interesting basis for further ECHOES activities and deliverables.

*Principles with a * are not directly formulated by the institutions themselves but paraphrased by our own hand from the textual sources.*

INSTITUTION	PRINCIPLE	DESCRIPTION (if available)
European political institutions		
European Union	Human dignity	Human dignity is inviolable. It must be respected, protected and constitutes the real basis of fundamental rights.
	Freedom	Freedom of movement gives citizens the right to move and reside freely within the Union. Individual freedoms such as respect for private life, freedom of thought, religion, assembly, expression and information are protected by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.
	Democracy	The functioning of the EU is founded on representative democracy. A European citizen automatically enjoys political rights. Every adult EU citizen has the right to stand as a candidate and to vote in elections to the European Parliament. EU citizens have the right to stand as a candidate and to vote in their country of residence, or in their country of origin.
	Equality	Equality is about equal rights for all citizens before the law. The principle of equality between women and men underpins all European policies and is the basis for European integration. It applies in all areas. The principle of equal pay for equal work became part of the Treaty of Rome in 1957.
	Rule of law	The EU is based on the rule of law. Everything the EU does is founded on treaties, voluntarily and democratically agreed by its EU countries. Law and justice are upheld by an independent judiciary. The EU countries gave final jurisdiction to the European Court of Justice - its judgments have to be respected by all.
	Human rights	Human rights are protected by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. These cover the right to be free from discrimination on the basis of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation, the right to the protection of your personal data, and the right to get access to justice.

Council of Europe	Democratic Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Democratic participation ensures regular, free, and fair elections conducted without fraud, adhering to national laws and European standards, such as the Venice Commission's Code of Good Practice in Electoral Matters. • Citizens are at the centre of governance, actively engaged in decision-making processes either directly or through legitimate representatives. Participation is inclusive, ensuring balanced representation of all genders and fostering the involvement of vulnerable and less privileged groups. • All voices are heard, and decisions are made in a way that reflects the will of the majority while safeguarding the rights and legitimate interests of the minority. • Public life is built on the freedoms of expression, assembly, and association, creating an environment where consensus can be reached to serve the best interests of the entire community.
	Human Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human rights, rooted in fairness, dignity, equality, and respect, are upheld in accordance with European and international standards, including the Council of Europe's Statute and the European Convention on Human Rights. • Legislation, institutions, and practices ensure the promotion, protection, and enjoyment of human rights, including environmental rights. Equality and inclusion are actively fostered, combating discrimination and hate while respecting diversity in all forms. • Strategies and plans with clear objectives and monitoring mechanisms support the participation of all genders, as well as less privileged and vulnerable groups, in building inclusive and fair societies.
	Rule of Law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rule of law ensures legal certainty and fairness, guaranteeing that all individuals are treated with dignity, equality, and proportionality. Laws are enacted through transparent, accountable, and democratic processes, with the separation of powers and judicial independence upheld nationwide. • Measures are in place to ensure equality before the law, prevent discrimination, and safeguard against arbitrariness or abuse of power by public authorities. • Administrative decisions are justified and transparent, contributing to a legal framework that fosters accountability and protects the rights of all individuals.
	Public Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The highest standards of public ethics are upheld, fostering trust in government, public institutions, and officials by ensuring they serve the public good above individual interests. • A comprehensive ethics framework is established, including strategies, laws, regulations, codes of conduct, and guidance that prioritize ethical practices in policy and decision-making processes, with attention to environmental considerations. • Clear procedures address complaints and grievances related to ethical breaches and conflicts of interest, both during and after public service. Measures are implemented to prevent and combat corruption, promote public awareness, and protect whistle-blowers from retaliation, ensuring accountability and integrity in public institutions.
	Accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accountability mechanisms ensure that governments, public institutions, and officials take responsibility for their actions and decisions, accepting appropriate consequences for any misconduct or omissions. • A clear accountability framework defines the responsibilities of local authorities and public officials, including their legal and financial obligations. Decisions are transparently reported, explained, and open to scrutiny, with the possibility of questioning or sanctions where necessary. • Proportionate remedies are in place to address inappropriate decisions or omissions, ensuring corrective actions are taken to uphold integrity and public trust.
	Openness and Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Openness and transparency are ensured by making government decision-making processes, public institutions, and officials' actions publicly accessible, in line with legal limitations necessary for a democratic society.

Council of Europe		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information is communicated clearly, accurately, and inclusively, ensuring it is secure and tailored to the needs of users. Public access to decisions, policies, and outcomes allows citizens to effectively follow and contribute to the work of local authorities, either directly or through representative bodies. • E-governance services leverage ICT tools to prioritize ease of use, quality, and data security while addressing e-literacy and privacy concerns in a cost-effective manner.
	Efficient, Effective, and Sound Administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient, effective, and sound administration is essential across all government and public institutions, ensuring the well-being of all citizens, without discrimination, and optimizing the use of public resources. • Strategic and operational plans define clear objectives and targets within specific timeframes, promoting resource optimization, effective coordination across governmental levels, and adherence to local democracy and sustainability goals. This guarantees the delivery of high-quality services at all levels. • Performance management systems are implemented to align with these objectives, with regular audits conducted at both internal and external levels. Quality legislation, compliant processes, and accessible offices ensure good administration and the protection of enforceable rights.
	Leadership, Capability, and Capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efforts to strengthen the leadership, capabilities, and capacities of government and public institutions are essential for effective democratic governance. • The local authority operates with a clear vision, inspired by the Principles of Good Democratic Governance, and fosters a proactive, innovative, and inclusive approach that reflects societal diversity. • Human resource policies are designed to align competencies with goals, promoting merit-based development. Regular assessments identify skills gaps, supported by training plans to enhance capabilities. • The necessary structures and processes for planning, funding, and evaluating capacity-building programs are in place. Performance management systems assess and reward individual performance while supporting both professional and personal development.
	Responsiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government, public institutions, and public officials must respond to the legitimate expectations and needs of the people they serve. • People's expectations and needs are consistently recognized and incorporated into public service planning and delivery through transparent processes. • Effective procedures are in place to oversee public services, including mechanisms for citizen complaints and engagement with Ombuds institutions. • Timely handling of monitoring outcomes and complaints is integrated throughout all stages of policy and decision-making.
	Sound Financial and Economic Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sound financial and economic management is crucial across government and public institutions to ensure the optimal use of public resources and policies that promote the well-being and prosperity of all citizens. • Economic and financial policies are aligned with other strategies, setting clear objectives to support long-term growth while safeguarding societal and environmental well-being, including intergenerational equity. • Internal and external audits are essential to ensure the soundness and coherence of financial management, assess risks, and provide assurance. • Cooperation and partnerships are actively pursued to identify economies of scale, ensure fair sharing of burdens and benefits, and reduce risks.
	Sustainability and Long-Term Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efforts should prioritize the sustainability of decisions made by government, public institutions, and officials, considering their impact on future generations and their ability to meet their own needs.

Council of Europe		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current policy and decision-making processes incorporate principles of resilience, sustainability, and intergenerational equity, acknowledging their impacts on administration, communities, and the environment, both now and in the future. • These processes also aim to preserve the historical, cultural, and societal aspects of the contexts they address. • Strategic planning includes key stakeholders and extends beyond electoral cycles to meet the future needs of people and communities.
	Openness to Change and Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government, public institutions, and public officials should proactively embrace change and innovation to improve public service resilience and quality, considering evolving expectations and realities, and engaging widely to enhance knowledge. • A climate of flexibility, self-evaluation, and continuous learning is fostered within public institutions, allowing them to adapt to changing contexts, external environments, and people's needs, in pursuit of better results. • The local authority actively engages in knowledge-sharing with public, private, and civil society actors, both domestically and internationally. • The local authority identifies, adapts, and implements successful practices, innovating in areas such as knowledge, institutional structures, management, tools, and methodologies when necessary.
European and international networks on cultural heritage and sciences		
E-RIHS	Excellence	Supporting outstanding projects. E-RIHS ERIC fosters excellence through support and continuity of outstanding research. An E-RIHS Certificate created at European level, will ensure support for outstanding large-scale/long-term projects requiring multiple accesses to the same or different facilities from the same or different platforms. This will enable research based on a combination of several visits to a facility and/or on-site campaigns, and continual access to archives and data. A balance of exploratory, medium- and longer-term projects will foster the development of knowledge on heritage materials and data as well as methodological innovations and will thus contribute to the creation of shared workflows, or "operational sequences". Additionally, excellence is ensured through a quick, efficient, and transparent proposal evaluation and selection process involving internationally leading experts.
	Competencies first	Considering skills as central. A distinct feature of E-RIHS ERIC is the interdisciplinary character of the interactions that develop among the different stakeholders involved in research. The required breadth of heritage science knowledge implies that the skills of all involved are equally valuable. External researchers are provided with all the required scientific and technical support, while internal researchers (access providers) need access to scholarly data and expertise, which often ends in interdisciplinary scientific collaboration. As a consequence, E-RIHS ERIC access project selection considers the competencies of all involved in the assessment of the proposal's feasibility. External researcher support starts during research proposal preparation developing questions related to sample requirement, suitable instruments and analytical techniques or duration of the proposed experiment. This requires training and communication. As most researchers enter the field at postgraduate or post-doctoral levels from a diverse range of fields, suitable specialized training opportunities are provided (both on-site and on-line). Training activities are tightly linked to infrastructure operation, allowing external researchers to optimally benefit from access. Particular care is given to training of staff managing and running E-RIHS ERIC facilities.

E-RIHS	Interdisciplinarity	Optimizing work for teams with complementary cultures and practices. Environmental, historical, and social contexts of heritage provide additional aspects of research supported by E-RIHS ERIC. As a model infrastructure for interdisciplinary research, E-RIHS ERIC bridges disciplines to advance heritage science and to contribute to the development of new knowledge and new methodologies. E-RIHS ERIC recognizes and supports teamwork at all stages of the process and fosters the use of its services by interdisciplinary teams, promoting a culture of exchange and cooperation. E-RIHS ERIC expects that interdisciplinarity will inspire new fields of research beyond heritage science, especially regarding instrumentation development, computing sciences, and the chemistry and physics of novel materials. E-RIHS ERIC might also bring new inspiration to environmental and geological sciences, which also study imprints from the past.
	Co-creation	Recognizing the contribution of each participant. Instead of a binary internal researcher (provider)/external researcher (user) relationship, E-RIHS ERIC fosters a culture of exchange and cooperation. Combining the expertise of the researchers accessing E-RIHS ERIC facilities and the scientists operating them is essential for the success of research. Scientific communities have a pivotal role in the stimulation of continuous improvement and innovation at the host facilities. Only by following this paradigm can new knowledge be co-created. As an example, E-RIHS will recommend by default that any knowledge resulting from their joint work is co-owned. External and internal researchers will by default co-own any knowledge resulting from their joint work.
	Engagement	Benefitting from the public-facing dimension of heritage. Cultural heritage is by definition managed by communities or accessed by the community through public-facing institutions like museums, galleries, libraries, archives, sites, and monuments. Therefore, it is perfectly suited to citizen science approaches, in line with the Open Science policies of the European Union. Heritage science contributes to the care of collections and sites in various ways, helping to extend knowledge and understanding of objects. It also contributes to the development of technologies enhancing access to heritage. This provides a direct route for exploitation of E-RIHS ERIC research in public-facing institutions. On the other side, citizens might play a relevant role in gathering, analyzing, or processing data in heritage science projects. Heritage institutions, as well as creative industries, can be drivers for innovation, providing ample opportunities for enhancing knowledge exchange and citizen involvement.
	Interoperability	Connecting knowledge. E-RIHS ERIC focuses on the interoperability of systems and instruments, addressing instrumental aspects, data storage, transfer capacities, data transparency and data quality. E-RIHS ERIC fosters interoperability of instruments to fully exploit the capacities of the research infrastructure and to match the needs of the scientific community. Being one of the main priorities for the European Commission in research and innovation, we see Open Science as a key enabler of interoperability. E-RIHS ERIC will promote the re-use of information, such as experimental plans, raw data, metadata, algorithms and their applications, to enable replicability and thus interoperability. This requires a long-term effort as fragmented practices using closed standards have been a barrier to openness in the heritage science community. E-RIHS ERIC will abide by the Heritage Data Re-Use Charter proposed by DARIAH and developed by infrastructures and projects in the heritage field.

E-RIHS	Innovation	Developing E-RIHS and heritage science. E-RIHS ERIC contributes to the development and adoption of new research methodologies, new interoperable instruments and digital tools, new methodologies and new techniques enabling improved understanding of heritage. To foster innovation, E-RIHS ERIC promotes the re-use of information and data fusion. Research activities will ensure that E-RIHS ERIC pushes the boundaries of innovation to offer the best possible infrastructure to the research community. E-RIHS ERIC fosters hybridization and multimodal approaches where coupled techniques and data fusion enable improved studies and understanding of heritage and heritage materials.
	Internationalisation	Collaborating at the global level. The challenges of heritage research and “the global lead that the EU holds in this field, supported today by an unstable combination of national and EU measures”, requires a joint and resolute effort. E-RIHS ERIC provides the framework for this to be implemented, having already established cooperation with International Organizations, including intergovernmental organizations such as the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). With the aim of developing advanced training activities, E-RIHS ERIC will also liaise with national and international professional bodies such as the Institute of Conservation (ICON), the International Institute for Conservation of Historic and Artistic Artworks (IIC) and the International Council of Museums (ICOM).
	Ethics	Respecting heritage values and encouraging responsible research. Heritage materials are specific as they are unique, non-renewable resources which contribute to identity at personal, local, national, European, and global levels. Consequently, working on heritage has direct ethical implications. E-RIHS intrinsically considers ethics in all its activities, and will ensure full conformity with international, national, and local legislation and promote the highest standards of ethical conduct.
	Quality	Guaranteeing the best external researcher (user) experience. E-RIHS will implement a quality control system applying the principles and options of quality management to all activities of the infrastructure, allowing all parties to have confidence in their results. To reach this purpose, the E-RIHS Quality Manual will be developed. It will guarantee the best external researcher (user) experience and allow all parties to have the greatest confidence in the processes and their results.
Europeana	Usable	Europeana provides the impetus, expertise and tools to support cultural heritage institutions in harnessing digital to open up their collections - to make them available to be used in new ways. Content and technology need to be accessible. They need to be easy-to-use and open, otherwise, the reach of any social or economic impact will be limited.
	Mutual	The Europeana Initiative is a networked organisation, a partnership of connected bodies and cultural heritage professionals. Europeana fosters creative collaboration and teamwork, working towards common goals for mutual benefit. Innovation needs to be community-based and reciprocal, combining the best of sector knowledge and practices.
	Reliable	Europeana supports the cultural heritage institutions that safeguard Europe’s heritage, those who organise it, structure it and make it accessible with great care and precision. Europeana is committed to ensuring that its digital data is always authentic, trustworthy and robust, that it’s easy to create with and that partners benefit from sharing it.

EOSC	Stakeholder-driven governance model*	[Governance framework] The EOSC governance framework will be co-designed, stakeholder driven and composed of three main layers: 1) institutional, including EU Member States and European Commission 2) operational, including an executive board and relevant working committees (e.g. thematic and functional) and 3) advisory, including a stakeholder forum.
	Accountability via co-funding mechanism*	[Funding] Over time, a co-funding mechanism mixing different revenue streams for the EOSC will be set up, to increase the accountability of the governance, building trust, sharing resources and building long-term capacity for European research data. Early implementation of the EOSC will pilot innovative business models and support an integrated data and service platform for European research.
	Strong and flexible governance model*	[Governance model] A long-term, sustainable research infrastructure in Europe requires a strong and flexible governance model based on trust and increasing mutuality. As interdisciplinarity is one of the main objectives of the EOSC, the governance model should be based on representativity, proportionality, accountability, inclusiveness and transparency.
	Long-term sustainability*	[Long-term sustainability] Research Funders will use existing and future resources strategically, to ensure long-term sustainability of open research data and research infrastructures, facilitating inter-disciplinarity.
	International vision*	[Global aspects] The EOSC will be European and open to the world, reaching out over time to relevant global research partners. It will increase the global value of open research data and support stakeholder engagement, including researchers and citizens. It will gradually widen the initiative to federated network of infrastructures and nodes from global research partners. The EOSC Stakeholder Forum will have an important role in this sense.
DARIAH	Enable digital arts and humanities research	<i>SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Integrate existing resources, research and services	<i>SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Use innovations from the national DARIAH partners and scale them to a European level	<i>SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Deliver methodological innovation and promote interdisciplinary research	<i>SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Stay digitally focused and analogue aware	<i>SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY PRINCIPLES</i>

DARIAH	Operate under a sustainable business model within the larger scientific community in Europe	<i>ORGANISATIONAL PRINCIPLES</i>
	Be receptive to community needs	<i>ORGANISATIONAL PRINCIPLES</i>
	Deliver easy to use services and resources	<i>ORGANISATIONAL PRINCIPLES</i>
	Delegate trust and share responsibilities	<i>ORGANISATIONAL PRINCIPLES</i>
	Display high quality services	<i>ORGANISATIONAL PRINCIPLES</i>
	Governed and led by the arts and humanities research community	<i>COMMUNITY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Become community-driven	<i>COMMUNITY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Be inclusive	<i>COMMUNITY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Promote openness	<i>COMMUNITY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Enable transnational collaboration	<i>COMMUNITY PRINCIPLES</i>
	Promote standards and best practices	<i>COMMUNITY PRINCIPLES</i>
JPI	Holistic approach	Cultural heritage has long been considered without regard to its environment, whilst the impact of human activities on natural areas has been neglected. It is therefore relevant to consider the links between cultural and natural heritage more closely than has been done in the past. Today, we talk about cultural landscape and consider heritage at a territorial level. Cultural heritage exists in combinations of tangible, intangible and digital forms. It is being produced continuously and contributes to the creation of identities.
	Collaborative and transdisciplinary research	Collaborative research with heritage professionals, NGOs, associations and a broad range of heritage institutions and management bodies (public and private) is encouraged. The priority research areas identified within SRIA 2020 should provide the space for investigator-led and curiosity-driven research across all disciplines within the JPI CH remit. Research should be truly integrative and provide opportunities to explore all forms of cultural heritage (tangible, intangible and digital) alongside its many interfaces with natural heritage and the environment. It should involve collaboration and work across disciplinary, conceptual, theoretical, methodological and international boundaries.

JPI	Public-led research and community engagement should be a catalyst for innovation and guarantee greater impact	Citizen science and the co-design and co-production of research are advocated. Knowledge sharing and co-creation are essential and a range of methods and educational tools to engage the broader public should be developed. Public and community engagement as well as participatory approaches should be at the core of activities and thought should be given to who creates knowledge, narrative and the role of communities in identifying, understanding and caring for heritage.
	Digital	Heritage researchers, whenever and wherever possible, should be applying and embedding new and emerging technologies and tools and exploring new methods for identification, knowledge, conservation and transmission as well as data gathering and analysis. Researchers should explore the role of artificial intelligence and new noninvasive, remote imaging and non-destructive measurement and testing techniques for archaeology, heritage and art. A critical digital studies approach should be taken which ensures that digital tools and outputs are accessible and sustainable.
	Education and training	The JPI CH aims to inspire a new generation of cultural heritage research and innovation actors across Europe through capacity building and formal and informal learning opportunities, in particular for young people. Research should provide opportunities for the provision of training to enable researchers to work across disciplines and all forms of heritage, and to support researchers at different stages of their careers. The JPI CH promotes inclusive research and diversity in researchers' gender, socio-economic and ethnic background.
	Communication, dissemination and impact	The JPI CH aims to build a culture that enables researchers to share their findings and demonstrate cultural, social, environmental and economic impact. They should be shared with and disseminated to researchers (including those in other disciplines), as well as to international stakeholders such as NGOs and users of cultural heritage, other industries, creators and the wider public including young people and hard-to-reach communities. There should be greater support for research to underpin the development of policies and guidelines for the preservation and use of cultural heritage.
	Working with other initiatives and infrastructure in Europe and beyond	The JPI CH encourages collaboration and the use of existing networks to avoid duplication, whilst also considering which new initiatives and infrastructure developments are needed. Research activities should link into existing infrastructure initiatives such as European Research Infrastructure for heritage science (E-RIHS), Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) and Europeana and European policies, laws and regulations. They should also build on and collaborate with funding initiatives such as Humanities in the European Research Area (HERA) and the other JPis and future EU research partnerships. The JPI CH aims to be a key actor in strengthening the heritage science ²² community and promoting heritage science as a field of research in its own right.
All European Academies (ALLEA)	Reliability	Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, methodology, analysis, and use of resources.
	Honesty	Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full, and unbiased way.
	Respect	Respect for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.

	Accountability	Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider societal impacts.
ICOMOS	Diversity and Interdisciplinarity	ICOMOS is made up of an enormously diverse range of people with varying, complementary professional and cultural backgrounds, from civil servants to academic researchers to private sector employees. Our members work together in a spirit of collegiality, respecting one another's diverse professional and technical knowledge, across cultures and belief systems.
	Impartiality	As an NGO, in all circumstances – and especially as one of the three World Heritage Convention Advisory Bodies – we rely on our members, whose professional experience and expertise, technical know-how and independence allow us to work with impartiality and according to a shared ethical code.
	Exchanges and Solidarity	At ICOMOS, we endeavour to bring people and cultures together. This involves facilitating the work and movement of members in disadvantaged or crisis situations. During major natural disasters and conflicts, ICOMOS' experts and specialists are mobilised to develop emergency measures for preserving, conserving and restoring damaged or at-risk heritage. This is also evidenced by our role as a founding member of the Blue Shield.
	Empowering the Next Generation	A key part of our mission at ICOMOS is to raise awareness of heritage and related challenges, and to exchange knowledge and know-how between generations. As such, we mentor emerging professionals, who are deeply involved with the issues at stake and in our different actions. Emerging professionals can be elected to positions of responsibility in their respective Committees as well as on the Board of ICOMOS, exchanging their know-how with more established members of the organisation.
	Access to Information	At ICOMOS, we believe that free and unrestricted access to scientific knowledge is fundamental to good heritage conservation. To enable this, we have our own open access archive platform, PUBLICOMOS. Additionally, ICOMOS' Documentation Centre offers a wealth of documentary resources, with over 40,000 titles and 40,000 graphic documents, World Heritage documents, and more.
NEMO	Collection value	<p><u>Our vision:</u> Tangible and intangible collections are at the heart of museums. NEMO wants to see that collections are well taken care of for present and future generations and are as widely accessible to all people as possible. They reflect different perspectives, cultural complexity and are used in multiple ways for the benefit of the society.</p> <p><u>Our concerns:</u> The collections are not seen as a core of the museum work and a funding priority by policy makers and funding organisations. The collection-related work does not always have adequate resources for taking proper care of their collections, developing and making optimal use of them.</p>

NEMO		<p><u>Our mission:</u> We advocate for the manifold values and uses of collections and provide a platform for museums to exchange good practices for the acquisition, deaccession, conservation, preservation, research, accessibility, interpretation, identification and innovative use of museum collections.</p>
	Social value	<p><u>Our vision:</u> Museums are part of a good life and provide social well-being. They communicate with all generations and serve society at large. They strengthen the social fabric and serve as places for meeting and dialogue for different cultures and offer opportunities for individual growth.</p> <p><u>Our concerns:</u> Museums are not fully acknowledged and supported in their role as social agents, they lack visibility and opportunities to cooperate with other sectors such as the health and the social sector.</p> <p><u>Our mission:</u> We highlight the social value and support the potential of museums for society by promoting their contribution to different social agendas such as health, tolerance, education, environment, democracy, active citizenship, social justice and poverty to policy makers and stakeholders from other sectors.</p>
	Educational value	<p><u>Our vision:</u> Museums help people develop as individuals and understand their place in the world. They are life-long learning environments, complementary to all other forms of education and they offer additional learning opportunities for all.</p> <p><u>Our concerns:</u> Museums are still not acknowledged and supported as an important agent in the educational system.</p> <p><u>Our mission:</u> We support museums to be recognised as rich learning environments and places of public engagement and provide the platform for the exchange of good practices.</p>
	Economic value	<p><u>Our vision:</u> Museums are important actors in the economy and the creative sectors. They are at the heart of successful urban regeneration and cultural tourism initiatives. They are places of, actors in and partners for the creative economy.</p> <p><u>Our concerns:</u> Museums are not fully acknowledged and supported as actors contributing positively to the economy and the creative sectors. There is still little comprehensive and comparable data available, and an appropriate framework to measure aggregate economic value and spill-over effects of museums is lacking.</p> <p><u>Our mission:</u> We want to ensure that museums are recognised for their positive impact on the economy and the creative industries and supports enhanced cooperation with partners to fully tap into museums' economic impact.</p>

NEMO	Digital transformation	<p><u>Our vision:</u> Digital technologies affect all aspects of museum work today. With their digital potential museums contribute to different social aspects as sources of creative innovation, information and all forms of learning. They interact with different audiences and promote open and democratic access to their collections on a global level.</p> <p><u>Our concerns:</u> Museums are lagging behind in fully tapping their digital potential, on an infrastructural, skills and knowledge and strategical level. To keep up with the exponential digital development museums have to fully embrace their digital extension. Public funding for digital transformation is scarce and should be made available for long term and experimental initiatives.</p> <p><u>Our mission:</u> We advocate for tailored regional, national and European funding long opportunities for museums with a focus on the development of digital skills and infrastructure of museums, including the development of sound metrics, frameworks and methods to track digital activities and success factors.</p>
	Professional development	<p><u>Our vision:</u> Museums contribute to a sense of belonging, shared values and solidarity among a society in constant change. The empowerment and capacity building of professionals who work in museums and take care of cultural heritage are at the core of successful museum work and meaningful social impact.</p> <p><u>Our concerns:</u> The importance of life-long learning and continuous training in all aspects of museum work to help museum professionals and the museum sector at large to embrace new societal developments and demands, and to enhance the value of museums to society, is not fully acknowledged and supported.</p> <p><u>Our mission:</u> We advocate for support through continuous and targeted capacity building programmes for museum professionals that will equip them with new and emerging skills as an integral part of contemporary museum work. We offer museum professionals European capacity building programmes to share experiences and knowledge and to foster a European dimension in museum work.</p>
	Sustainable transition	<p><u>Our vision:</u> The consequences of climate change have a dramatic ecological and social impact on every sector and element of society and museums and the work of museum professionals are not an exception. Adaptations to museum operations are key to preserve the impact of collections and knowledge for the benefit of future generations. The potential of museums to educate, engage and activate the public to act for a sustainable future should be adequately acknowledged, supported, and streamlined in museum practice and strategy.</p>

NEMO		<p><u>Our concerns:</u> Museums have not been adequately supported by governing and funding institutions to make a successful sustainable transition, nor has their potential to support the sustainable transition of our society been fully acknowledged.</p> <p><u>Our mission:</u> We advocate for the potential of museums to be key actors in the fight against climate change and to be supported to tap their full potential through policies and funding programmes supporting Europe's sustainable transition. We help museums create awareness, exchange and build capacities as they adapt to climate friendly operations and use their platform to incorporate the urgency and action necessary to prevent further global temperature increase, biodiversity loss and consequent social and ecological casualties.</p>
E.C.C.O.	Social value	Our Vision: Cultural heritage safeguarded for society through high standards in the professional practice of Conservation-Restoration.
	Quality professional practice	Our Vision: Cultural heritage safeguarded for society through high standards in the professional practice of Conservation-Restoration.
	Professional development	Our Mission: To organize, develop and promote, on a practical, scientific and cultural level, the profession of the Conservator-Restorer. To set standards and regulate practice at European level and enhance communication between and mobility of professionals. To strengthen the role and responsibilities of the Conservator-Restorer in relation to others in safeguarding cultural heritage.
	Quality professional practice/Standards	Our Mission: To organize, develop and promote, on a practical, scientific and cultural level, the profession of the Conservator-Restorer. To set standards and regulate practice at European level and enhance communication between and mobility of professionals. To strengthen the role and responsibilities of the Conservator-Restorer in relation to others in safeguarding cultural heritage.
	Social/professional accountability	Our Mission: To organize, develop and promote, on a practical, scientific and cultural level, the profession of the Conservator-Restorer. To set standards and regulate practice at European level and enhance communication between and mobility of professionals. To strengthen the role and responsibilities of the Conservator-Restorer in relation to others in safeguarding cultural heritage.
	Professional accountability	Strategic goals: E.C.C.O.'s work focuses on the role of Conservator-Restorers in the safeguarding of cultural heritage and their relationship with other professions in the field.
	Quality professional practice/Social value	Strategic goals: Quality derives from an ethical approach that ensures a consistently high standard of work and its results, achieved in an accountable manner.
	Open communication/Accessibility and participation	Strategic goals: Every aspect of our work relies on open communication towards our member organisations, affiliated organisations, European governmental bodies and the broader community. Advocacy of our goals can only be effective when we have a high level of visibility.

E.C.C.O.	Quality professional practice/mobility	Strategic goals: A conservator-restorer with recognized competence is entitled to work anywhere throughout Europe. Greater mobility is achieved via the mutual recognition of qualifications.
	Rule of Law/professional accountability/Social value	Strategic goals: The impact of legislation and European directives on the Conservator-Restorers' profession, including the legal obligations, has specific significance for cultural heritage and the practice of Conservation-Restoration.
	Advocacy/Social accountability	Strategic goals: Guidance means a proactive approach in giving advice and in developing tools and recommendations to the benefit of E.C.C.O.'s member organisations.
European Data Space	Self Determination	
	Data sovereignty	
	Privacy	
	Trust	
	Transparency	
	Security	
	Fair competition	
	Consumer protection	
	Fundamental rights	
	Citizen participation and empowerment	
	Innovation	
	Sustainability	
	Openness	
Data altruism		
	Preservation and promotion*	Museums preserve, interpret and promote the natural and cultural inheritance of humanity.

ICOM <i>Code of conduct</i>	Public benefit*	Museums that maintain collections hold them in trust for the benefit of society and its development.
	Knowledge*	Museums hold primary evidence for establishing and furthering knowledge.
	Opportunities*	Museums provide opportunities for the appreciation, understanding and management of the natural and cultural heritage. Museums hold resources that provide opportunities for other public services and benefits.
	Communities*	Museums work in close collaboration with the communities from which their collections originate as well as those they serve.
	Legality*	Museums operate in a legal manner.
	Professionalism*	Museums operate in a professional manner.
ICOM <i>Strategic Plan</i>	International outlook*	We are international in outlook.
	Professional focus*	We are professional in focus.
	Collaboration*	We are collaborative in practice.
European Association of Archaeologists	Preservation*	It is the duty of every archaeologist to ensure the preservation of the archaeological heritage by every legal means.
	Communication*	In achieving that end archaeologists will take active steps to inform the general public at all levels of the objectives and methods of archaeology in general and of individual projects in particular, using all the communication techniques at their disposal.
	Professional excellence*	Where preservation is impossible, archaeologists will ensure that investigations are carried out to the highest professional standards. Archaeologists will carry out their work to the highest standards recognised by their professional peers.
	Impact*	In carrying out such projects, archaeologists will wherever possible, and in accordance with any contractual obligations that they may have entered into, carry out prior evaluations of the ecological and social implications of their work for local communities.
	Anti-trafficking*	Archaeologists will not engage in, or allow their names to be associated with, any form of activity relating to the illicit trade in antiquities and works of art, covered by the 1970 UNESCO Convention on the means of prohibiting and preventing the illicit import, export, and transfer of ownership of cultural property.
	Non-profit*	Archaeologists will not engage in, or allow their names to be associated with, any activity that impacts the archaeological heritage which is carried out for commercial profit which derives directly from or exploits the archaeological heritage itself.

European Association of Archaeologists	Collaboration with authorities*	It is the responsibility of archaeologists to draw the attention of the competent authorities to threats to the archaeological heritage, including the plundering of sites and monuments and illicit trade in antiquities, and to use all the means at their disposal to ensure that action is taken in such cases by the competent authorities.
	State-of-the-art*	Archaeologists have a duty to keep themselves informed of developments in knowledge and methodology relating to their field of specialisation and to techniques of fieldwork, conservation, information dissemination, and related areas.
	Training*	Archaeologists should not undertake projects for which they are not adequately trained or prepared.
	Research organisation*	A research design should be formulated as an essential prelude to all projects. Arrangements should also be made before starting projects for the subsequent storage and curation of finds, samples, and records in accessible public repositories (museums, archive collections, etc).
	Record-keeping*	Proper records, prepared in a comprehensible and durable form, should be made of all archaeological projects.
	Reporting*	Adequate reports on all projects should be prepared and made accessible to the archaeological community as a whole with the minimum delay through appropriate conventional and/or electronic publishing media, following an initial period of confidentiality not exceeding six calendar months.
	Accessibility of results*	Archaeologists will have prior rights of publication in respect of projects for which they are responsible for a reasonable period, not exceeding ten years. During this period they will make their results as widely accessible as possible and will give sympathetic consideration to requests for information from colleagues and students, provided that these do not conflict with the primary right of publication. When the ten-year period has expired, the records should be freely available for analysis and publication by others.
	Source acknowledgment*	Written permission must be obtained for the use of original material and acknowledgement to the source included in any publication.
	Anti-discrimination*	In recruiting staff for projects, archaeologists shall not practise any form of discrimination based on sex, religion, age, race, disability, or sexual orientation.
	Employment safety*	The management of all projects must respect national standards relating to conditions of employment and safety.
National and regional institutions		
Heritage Council of Ireland	Integrity	We embrace the ideals of integrity, accountability and transparency in all our activities. We commit to working honestly, collaboratively and respectfully with colleagues and partners.
	Diversity and Inclusion	Our 21st-century Irish nation is an exciting mix of ethnicities and origins. We delight in diversity, we embrace it as we seek to learn from other cultures. The reach of heritage includes all citizens, whatever their age, background, physical or emotional needs. We believe in a person-centred advocacy, in empowering communities by honouring their place in our land.

	Collaboration	We engage in meaningful partnerships with local authorities and a range of other collaborators in pursuit of our many shared objectives. We commit to working with the custodians of heritage in public and private ownership, and in the care of communities.
	Care	We commit to promoting an integrated approach to heritage protection, conservation and interpretation, bringing together natural, cultural, intangible and built heritage. This reflects our remit as outlined in the Heritage Act of 1995.
Historic Environment Scotland	Conservation*	Actions taken in respect of Scotland's historic environment should secure its conservation and management for the benefit and enjoyment of present and future generations
	Preservation*	There should be a presumption in favour of preservation of individual historic assets and also the pattern of the wider historic environment; no historic asset should be lost or radically changed without adequate consideration of its significance and of all the means available to manage and conserve it
	Sustainability*	Scotland's historic environment should be managed in a sustainable way, recognising that it is a social, cultural, economic and environmental resource of great value
	Accessibility*	All of the people of Scotland should be able to enjoy, appreciate, learn from and understand Scotland's historic environment, and be assisted in that through access, research, knowledge, information and education and proactive conservation investment, without compromise to cultural significance
Fondazione Scuola dei beni e delle attività culturali (Italy)	Honesty and fairness	L'onestà e la correttezza rappresentano principi etici di riferimento per tutte le attività poste in essere dalla Scuola per il perseguimento dei propri fini istituzionali. I Destinatari svolgono la propria attività nell'interesse e nel rispetto della missione istituzionale della Scuola e non dovranno versare o accettare somme di denaro, esercitare altre forme di corruzione, fare o accettare doni o favori a terzi o da parte di terzi allo scopo di procurare vantaggi, diretti o indiretti, alla Scuola, a sé stessi o a terzi.
	Confidentiality/Privacy	La Scuola si impegna ad osservare il principio della riservatezza delle informazioni e dei dati personali oggetto di trattamento e la protezione delle informazioni acquisite in relazione all'attività prestata, uniformandosi alle prescrizioni in materia di riservatezza dei dati personali di cui al D. Lgs. n. 196 del 2003, disciplinante il "Codice in materia di protezione dei dati personali" (e successive modificazioni, integrazioni e regolamenti attuativi) nonché alle previsioni del Regolamento UE n. 2016/679 ("GDPR"). I Destinatari sono tenuti a non utilizzare le informazioni ed i dati acquisiti in occasione del loro rapporto con la Scuola per vantaggi o interessi propri o di terzi, per arrecare danno alla Scuola o per finalità estranee alla loro attività all'interno della Scuola.
	Transparency	La Scuola si impegna ad informare in modo efficace e trasparente tutti i portatori di interesse rendendo disponibili gli elementi più rilevanti della propria attività e del proprio andamento economico e gestionale.
	Fighting corruption and conflicts of interest	La Scuola si impegna a mettere in atto tutte le misure necessarie a prevenire ed evitare fenomeni di corruzione e di conflitto di interesse. Chi opera presso la Scuola deve evitare, nello svolgimento dei propri incarichi o funzioni, qualsiasi situazione

Fondazione Scuola dei beni e delle attività culturali (Italy)		che possa dar luogo a conflitti di interesse ed è obbligato a informare tempestivamente gli Organi della Scuola delle situazioni o attività in cui potrebbe essere titolare, direttamente o indirettamente, di interessi in conflitto con quelli della Scuola stessa.
	Impartiality	La Scuola, in applicazione del principio di imparzialità e di parità di trattamento, evita ogni forma di discriminazione connessa all'età, al sesso, alla sessualità, allo stato di salute, allo stato civile, alla razza, alle opinioni politiche e al credo religioso.
	Enhancement of human resources and personal integrity	La Scuola tutela e promuove il valore delle risorse umane al fine di accrescere il patrimonio di competenze di ciascun dipendente e promuove, al proprio interno, il rispetto dell'integrità fisica, morale e culturale della persona. La Scuola garantisce ad ogni soggetto condizioni di lavoro e di frequenza dei corsi rispettose della dignità individuale ed ambienti di lavoro sicuri.
	Teachers' responsibility in training activities	I docenti collaboratori della Scuola sono tenuti a svolgere le attività didattiche in piena aderenza agli elevati requisiti di professionalità richiesti dalle attività formative svolte dalla Scuola e tenendo conto degli interessi e delle esigenze degli allievi.
	Merit enhancement	La Scuola riconosce e promuove il merito sia come dote individuale sia come capacità di relazionarsi ad altri e di operare in modo collegiale quale criterio essenziale di valorizzazione personale e professionale ed adotta adeguati strumenti di controllo dello stesso. Con riferimento alla selezione e valutazione degli allievi, al reclutamento del personale e dei collaboratori ed alle progressioni di carriera, il merito costituisce parametro unico di valutazione e di selezione.
	Image protection	La Scuola richiede a tutti i soggetti interni o esterni di rispettare il nome ed il prestigio della stessa, astenendosi da comportamenti suscettibili di lederne l'immagine. Non è consentito l'utilizzo del nome o del logo della Scuola per scopi non istituzionali. I dipendenti, i collaboratori e gli allievi della Scuola non rilasciano, attraverso qualsiasi mezzo d'informazione e comunicazione, dichiarazioni in nome della Scuola senza espressa autorizzazione dei competenti Organi della Scuola stessa. I Destinatari sono tenuti ad utilizzare tutti i mezzi di comunicazione, compresi i social media, in modo corretto e nel rispetto della Scuola e della riservatezza delle persone, e a non diffondere informazioni, testi o immagini lesive del prestigio e della reputazione della Scuola.
	Anti-Money Laundering	La Scuola esercita la propria attività nel pieno rispetto delle vigenti normative antiriciclaggio e delle disposizioni emanate dalle Autorità competenti.
	Minimally invasive/damaging research methods*	The purposes and consequences of all archaeological research should be carefully considered before the beginning of work. Approaches and methods should be chosen that require a minimum of damage to the archaeological record. Although excavation is sometimes the appropriate means of research, archaeological survey, study of previously excavated material, and other means should be considered before resort is made to excavation.
	Appropriate qualifications*	The recovery and study of archaeological material from all periods should be carried out only under the supervision of qualified personnel.

Archaeological Institute of America (North America)	Adequate and accessible long-term storage*	Archaeologists should anticipate and provide for adequate and accessible long-term storage and curatorial facilities for all archaeological materials, records, and archives, including machine-readable data, which require specialized archival care and maintenance.
	Publicity of results*	Archaeologists should make public the results of their research in a timely fashion, making evidence available to others if publication is not accomplished within a reasonable time.
	Conservation/preservation*	All research projects should contain specific plans for conservation, preservation, and publication from the very outset, and funds should be secured for such purposes.
	Outreach*	Professional archaeologists should engage in public outreach through lecturing, popular writing, school programs, and other educational initiatives.
	Ecological sustainability*	Plans for field work should consider the ecological impact of the project and its overall impact on the local communities.
	Consultation of communities*	For field projects, archaeologists should consult with appropriate representatives of the local community during the planning stage, invite local participation in the project, and regularly inform the local community about the results of the research.
	Respect of communities*	Archaeologists should respect the cultural norms and dignity of local inhabitants in areas where archaeological research is carried out.
	Balance of interests*	The legitimate concerns of people who claim descent from, or some other connection with, cultures of the past must be balanced against the scholarly integrity of the discipline. A mutually acceptable accommodation should be sought.
	Fairness*	Archaeologists involved in cooperative projects should strive for harmony and fairness; those in positions of authority should behave with consideration toward those under their authority, while all team members should strive to promote the success of the broader undertaking.
	Safety*	The Principal Investigator(s) of archaeological projects should maintain acceptable standards of safety and ascertain that staff members are adequately insured.
	Confidentiality*	Professional archaeologists should maintain confidentiality of information gleaned in reviewing grant proposals and other such privileged sources.
	Anti-discrimination*	Professional archaeologists should not practice discrimination or harassment based on sex, religion, age, race, national origin, disability, or sexual orientation; project sponsors should establish the means to eliminate and/or investigate complaints of discrimination or harassment.
Accessibility*	Archaeologists should honor reasonable requests from colleagues for access to materials and records, preserving existing rights to publication, but sharing information useful for the research of others. Scholars seeking access to unpublished information should not expect to receive interpretive information if that is also unpublished and in progress.	

Archaeological Institute of America (North America)	Lawfulness/respect for professional norms*	Before studying and/or publishing any unpublished material archaeologists should secure proper permission, normally in writing, from the appropriate project director or the appointed representative of the sponsoring institution and/or the antiquities authorities in the country of origin.
	Internal communication*	Scholars studying material from a particular site should keep the project director informed of their progress and intentions; project directors should return the courtesy.
	Collegiality*	Members of cooperative projects should prepare and evaluate reports in a timely and collegial fashion.
	Ethics*	In their research and publications professional archaeologists should adhere to the guidelines of the AIA Code of Ethics concerning illegal antiquities.
	Non-profit*	Professional archaeologists should not participate in projects whose primary goal is private gain. This does not apply to cultural resource management and similar projects, even if carried out by a for-profit firm, as long as they otherwise comply with the provisions of the Code of Professional Standards.
	Anti-plagiarism*	Professional archaeologists must not engage in plagiarism or the fabrication or falsification of data. Professional archaeologists should be explicit and accurate in acknowledging their use of words, ideas, data, and research findings of other scholars, and they should respect the property rights of copyright holders. Intellectual integrity requires the accurate and truthful reporting of the results of excavation and scholarship.
Institute on Governance (Canada)	Legitimacy and voice	This principle has six criteria. The first, existence of a supportive democratic and human rights context, refers to the presence of democratic institutions based on a viable multi-party system, human rights, promotion of tolerance, respect for existing rights, and the absence of discrimination based on gender, race, color, ethnicity or religion. The second, appropriate degree of decentralization in decision-making, necessitates that any devolution is through local bodies accountable to local people and that have the capacity to perform their functions. The third, collaborative management in decision-making, requires the involvement of representatives of all affected parties. The fourth, citizen participation at all levels, involves local levels of involvement and equal gender participation. The fifth, existence of civil society groups and an independent media, is of importance in balancing the exercise of powers granted to political leaders and managers. Finally, the sixth criterion, high levels of trust, requires confidence amongst all stakeholders.
	Direction	This principle comprises five criteria. The first, consistency with international direction, requires compliance with international conventions and other guidance documents. The second, existence of legislative direction, requires regulations that set out clear objectives, establish clear authority, provide viable administration, include citizen-participation and are available in written form. The third, existence of system-wide plans, entails the presence of quantified objectives for management, established priorities for planning periods, and citizen participation in their implementation. The fourth, existence of management plans, requires that goals have formal approval by appropriate authorities, clear objectives consistent with legislation, and measurable results within given timeframes. The goals must also be reviewed and updated on a regular cycle, and be implemented through annual workplans. The fifth, demonstration of effective leadership, requires that

Institute on Governance (Canada)		politicians and managers provide consistent vision for the development of subject sites, mobilize support, and provide resources for implementation.
	Performance	This principle consists of eight criteria. The first, cost effectiveness, refers to efficiency in the achievement of objectives. The second, capacity, refers to the ability of the responsible agency to undertake required functions. It also refers to policy capacity and the adequacy and security of funding. The third, co-ordination, is the ability to synchronize the efforts of players. The fourth, performance information to the public, requires provision of sufficient information for the public to assess progress. The fifth, Responsiveness, refers to an agency's ability and inclination to deal with complaints and public criticism. The sixth, monitoring and evaluation, is the capacity to undertake regular and comprehensive review of progress toward goals, and to respond to findings. The seventh, adaptive management, is the ability to learn and adjust management based on experience. Finally, the eighth criterion, risk management, is the capacity to identify key potential problems and to prepare for them.
	Accountability	This principle comprises six criteria. The first, clarity, refers to unequivocal assignment of responsibilities and authority. The second, coherence and breadth, is the degree to which wider concepts of responsibility to the global community, future generations and the environment are integrated with concepts of political accountability. The third, role of political leaders, is the appropriateness of responsibilities assigned to elected representatives as opposed to non-elected officials. It also refers to the absence of corruption. The fourth, public institutions of accountability, means open access to information and the capacity to analyze and report. The fifth, civil society and the media, refers to the effectiveness of non-governmental bodies and the press in mobilizing demand for accountability. The sixth criterion, Transparency, is the capacity of citizens, civil society and the media to access relevant information.
	Fairness	This principle consists of four criteria. First is the existence of a supportive judicial context, a legal system characterized by respect for the rule of law. The rule of law encompasses an independent judiciary, equality before the law, the requirement for government to base its actions on well-defined legal authorities, and the right of citizens to seek legal remedies against the government and against their fellow citizens. The second criterion, fair, impartial and effective enforcement of rules, includes the transparency of the rules themselves, the absence of corruption among public officials, and the right of appeal for those charged with transgressions. The third criterion, fairness in the process for establishing new conservation sites, includes respect for the rights, uses and traditional knowledge of local peoples, an assessment of other options for the use of the area, public participation in the process and appropriate balance among protected site objectives. The fourth criterion, fairness in the management of conservation sites, includes achieving a favorable balance of costs and benefits to local peoples, mechanisms for sharing or devolving management decision-making with local peoples, equitable human resource management practices for staff, and processes for recognizing and dealing with past injustices resulting from the establishment of conservation sites.
	Ethics*	A member shall adhere to high standards of ethical and responsible behaviour in the conduct of archaeological affairs.
	Conservation*	The member has a responsibility for the conservation of the historic environment.

Institute for Archaeologists (UK)	Recording*	The member shall conduct his/her work in such a way that reliable information about the past may be acquired, and shall ensure that the results be properly recorded.
	Accessibility*	The member has responsibility for making available the results of archaeological work with reasonable dispatch.
	Career opportunities*	The member shall recognise the aspirations of employees, colleagues and helpers with regard to all matters relating to employment, including career development, health and safety, terms and conditions of employment and equality of opportunity.
Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland	Architects shall act with honesty and integrity when providing architectural services in connection with their profession.	<p>1.1 Architects shall maintain and advance their knowledge of the art and science of architecture, respect the body of architectural accomplishment, contribute to its growth and give precedence to learned and independent professional judgement over any other motive in the pursuit of the art, science, and business of architecture.</p> <p>1.2 Architects shall ensure that they continually maintain and develop their professional knowledge and skill, in all areas relevant to their practice in the State, to the standards established by the RIAI.</p> <p>1.3 Architects shall continually seek to raise their standards of excellence in all relevant areas including architectural education, research, training, design, technology, construction methods and practice.</p> <p>1.4 Architects shall ensure that they have appropriate and effective procedures such as enable them to discharge their obligations under the Code.</p> <p>1.5 An architect is an independent professional and must be allowed to make independent professional judgements. Allowance has to be made for legitimate differences in professional opinion.</p> <p>1.6 Architects should not, in an architectural practice, be a partner, shadow-director, ordinary director or take up employment with an unsuitable person or persons, such as a person whose name has been erased from the Register of Architects as a result of a disciplinary decision or convicted of a relevant criminal offence.</p>
	Architects shall be aware of the social, environmental and economic impact of architectural activities.	<p>2.1 Whilst architects' primary responsibility is to their clients, they should nevertheless have due regard to their wider responsibility to conserve and enhance the environment.</p> <p>2.2 Architects shall not communicate or promote or represent themselves or their professional services in a false, misleading or deceptive manner, nor shall they allow others to do so if acting on their behalf.</p> <p>2.3 Architects shall avoid, at all times, any action or situation which is inconsistent with their professional obligations or which is likely to raise doubts about their independence, impartiality or integrity.</p> <p>2.4 Architects shall not make, support or acquiesce in any statement, written or otherwise, which is contrary to their own knowledge or professional opinion or which they know to be misleading or unfair to others or otherwise discreditable to the profession or their client or user.</p>

<p>Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland</p>		<p>2.5 Architects shall not promote, encourage, support or acquiesce in any act which is likely to assist in the commission of a crime or of unethical conduct.</p>
	<p>Architects shall uphold the integrity and dignity of the profession.</p>	<p>3.1 Architects in the practice of their profession, shall pursue their professional activities with independence, impartiality, confidentiality, integrity, honesty and fairness at all times.</p> <p>3.2 Architects, in providing a professional service and in safeguarding a client's legitimate interests, shall comply with all relevant statutory procedures and regulations in the State.</p> <p>3.3 Architects shall act fairly and impartially when administering a contract or otherwise acting between parties.</p> <p>3.4 Architects shall have regard to the RIAI's published client/architect agreements when proposing to a client the services to be provided. Sample copies of these agreements can be viewed on the RIAI website. Architects are not required to utilise these documents, but when proposing services to be provided they should include at a minimum the following: • The scope of the work • The fee or method of calculating fees • Description and allocation of the responsibilities of client, architect and other consultants • Any limitation of responsibilities • Payment stages and terms of payment • Provisions for termination • Any special or unusual factors • Information on dispute resolution procedures • Projected timescales for delivery of stages of the service • Architects should be aware of their professional responsibility to inform their clients, when agreeing an appointment, if the range of issues covered in RIAI Client/Architect Agreements</p> <p>3.5. Architects shall not be party to any arrangement which provides for the payment of professional fees by or through a contractor except when the contractor is the client.</p> <p>3.6. Architects shall not be party to any arrangement which involves the giving or receipt of an improper inducement in any form.</p> <p>3.7. Architects shall not offer or give consideration for the introduction of clients.</p> <p>3.8. Architects shall not abuse an office or position of trust to attract potential clients.</p> <p>3.9 Architects shall not accept a commission if, by reason of office or position, they could grant or influence the granting of any form of statutory or other approval or assistance for the commission.</p> <p>3.10 Architects shall not imply skills not attested to by their qualifications or experience or use such qualifications in a misleading way.</p> <p>3.11 Architects shall not engage in any business which could lead to a conflict of interest or be inconsistent with the proper discharge of their professional responsibilities and the maintenance of their professional independence.</p> <p>3.12 Architects practicing in any form of association with a person who is not an architect shall ensure that the agreement controlling such association incorporates a requirement that the Code of Professional Conduct is observed in all matters pertaining to the practice.</p> <p>3.13 Architects shall maintain, at all times, a reasonable level of professional skill and competence, at least to the standards established by the RIAI.</p>

		<p>3.14 Architects should not publish or cause to be published any promotional material or advertisements which: are false or misleading in any respect; are likely to bring the architectural profession into disrepute; reflect unfavourably on other architects.</p> <p>For the avoidance of doubt nothing in this Code should be used to prevent normal procompetitive practice and normal commercial practice.</p> <p>3.15 Architects may bring their practice to the notice of potential clients provided that the application is not in respect of a project for which they could reasonably know that an architect has already been commissioned.</p> <p>3.16 Architects may allow their name or practice-name to be inserted in any classified list of architects.</p> <p>3.17 Architects shall practice as sole trader, body corporate, firm or partnership only in compliance with the rules as issued by the RIAI in accordance with the Building Control Act 2007, Section 18(6).</p>
<p>Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland</p>	<p>Architects shall honourably discharge their responsibilities to the client or employer.</p>	<p>4.1 Architects shall conduct their architectural practice and deal with clients in a professional and efficient manner. In particular architects shall keep clients regularly informed of the progress of work undertaken on their behalf.</p> <p>4.2 Architects shall treat the affairs of a client or employer in strict confidence.</p> <p>4.3 Architects shall not, without the agreement of the client or employer, use to their own advantage confidential information gained in the course of their association.</p> <p>4.4 Architects who have a personal, business or financial interest in a matter referred to them for their advice or services shall disclose such interest to the relevant client or employer.</p> <p>4.5 Architects may limit their liability provided always that it is done within the spirit and intention of the Code.</p> <p>4.6 Architects shall be mindful at all times that the honourable discharge of responsibility to a client demands reasonable standards of professional practice.</p> <p>4.7 Architects, before accepting an architectural commission, shall satisfy themselves that they can provide the technical, financial and administrative resources required to complete it to a reasonable professional standard.</p> <p>4.8 Architects, when undertaking an architectural commission shall, as soon as is reasonably practicable, confirm in writing the scope of the professional services to be provided, the fee arrangements, the target or other cost limit for the project, work or services and, as appropriate, the essential requirements of the project and any special circumstances and conditions relevant to the commission.</p> <p>4.9 Where an architect considers it necessary to engage specialist expertise on the client's behalf the architect shall inform the client or employer before entering into any agreement with such specialist.</p> <p>4.10 Architects should respond promptly and courteously to a client's complaint in relation to the architect's professional service.</p>

<p>Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland</p>		<p>4.11 If so requested, Architects should provide a client or employer with information on how to obtain a copy of the Code of Professional Conduct and of the complaints procedures available from the Registration Body.</p> <p>4.12 Architects should not engage in architectural practice unless adequate and appropriate professional indemnity insurance cover as established by the RIAI and confirmed annually as may be required by the RIAI is in place.</p> <p>4.13 Sole practitioners should have arrangements in place for the conduct of their business in the event of incapacity or other absence from work.</p> <p>4.14 Architects should ensure that their professional finances are managed prudently, so as not to be to the detriment of a client. Examples of matters which may be examined to establish whether they might indicate a wilful disregard for responsibility or integrity by an architect include: an order of bankruptcy, the liquidation of a company of which they are a director other than for the purposes of reconstruction or amalgamation, an accommodation with creditors, including voluntary arrangements, failure to pay a judgement debt.</p> <p>4.16 Architects should carry out their professional work without undue delay and, so far as it is within their power, within an agreed reasonable time limit.</p> <p>4.17 When an architect offers, or is part of such offer, a service combining architectural services with building/construction contracting services, the architect should confirm in writing to all relevant parties that their services will not include the independent functions of an architect.</p> <p>4.18 Nothing in this Code shall prevent an architect from resigning from a project or terminating an appointment provided reasonable notice is given</p>
	<p>Architects shall act honourably towards their colleagues.</p>	<p>5.2 If required or on being required by a client to proceed with work on which the member has reason to believe, or ascertain by reasonable enquiry, another architect is engaged, the architect shall immediately take all reasonable steps to so inform such other architect and shall record the action taken.</p> <p>5.3 An architect, if approached to give an opinion on the work of another architect, shall notify that architect, unless it is prejudicial to the interest of the client to do so.</p> <p>5.4 Architects practicing in any form of professional association shall ensure that a formal partnership or corporate agreement is in place and is kept up to date.</p> <p>5.5 Architects, before undertaking an architectural collaboration directly with other architects, shall ensure that a written agreement is in place defining the nature of the collaboration, the manner in which the work will be allocated and fees shared between the parties, and the attribution of design responsibility and credits.</p> <p>5.6 Architects who collaborate with others in the design of a building project shall ensure that any publicity relating to it accurately and fairly reflects the contribution of their colleagues.</p> <p>5.7 Criticism of a colleague's work should only be made in the context of a reasoned debate or review.</p>

<p>Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland</p>		<p>5.8 Architects shall regard the design of a building or complex as the intellectual property of the architect responsible for it. Before undertaking a commission to carry out the design of another architect or to make material changes to an existing building designed by another architect, architects shall take all reasonable steps to notify that architect.</p> <p>5.9 “The infringement of the intellectual property rights of another architect is unethical and a breach of the Code”.</p>
	<p>Architects shall promote the standards of this Code.</p>	<p>6.1 Architects should conduct their professional work in accordance with this Code and, subject to any restrictions imposed by law or the courts, report to the Registrar any serious breach of the Code which may come to their notice.</p> <p>6.2 Where an architect is appointed as an arbitrator, adjudicator, mediator, conciliator or expert witness and is in receipt of privileged information, their duty in that role may take precedence over any requirement to report breaches of the Code to the Registrar.</p> <p>6.3 An architect should not (except in the circumstances described at 6.2 above) enter into a contract other than a settlement of a dispute, the terms of which would prevent any party from reporting an apparent breach of the Code by another architect to the Registrar.</p>